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THE LIVED COMMUNICATION EXPERIENCES OF SPECIAL EDUCATION
TEACHERS AT MILLER COUNTY SCHOOLS

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Acceptance Page

This dissertation titled "**THE LIVED COMMUNICATION EXPERIENCES OF SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS AT MILLER COUNTY SCHOOLS**" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Doctor of Communication (DCOMM).

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Rom

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

Rom Kenneth B. Sales has been teaching since 2009. He finished his degree in Secondary Education major in English in the Philippines, graduating as Summa cum Laude and Class Valedictorian. He also won the university's Leadership Award. He went on to pursue his Masters in Teaching English Language and Literature. He also finished two doctorate degrees before taking up Doctorate in Communication at UPOU. He finished Doctor of Philosophy in Development Education and Doctor of Development Education major in Special Education.

After graduating from college, he became a college instructor in the Philippines for a year. Then, he taught as an English Instructor at University Malaysia Perlis (2010-2012). He then moved to Thailand to work as an International Program Coordinator and English Instructor at King Mongkut's University of Technology Thonburi (2012-2017). He decided to return to high school teaching and became an English teacher and department head at Roong Aroon School, Bangkok (2017-2021). After residing in Thailand for almost a decade, he moved to the United States where he taught at Monroe High School, Albany, Georgia for a year as an English Language Arts (ELA) teacher. Currently, he teaches ELA at Miller County High School, Colquitt, Georgia. He holds teaching licenses in the Philippines, Thailand, Georgia, Arizona, Colorado, and New Mexico.

Apart from language teaching, he has also coached various debate teams over the years. He started as a debate himself, winning various national and international tournaments. He has also won national competitions as an adjudicator and judged international competitions.

His previous researches include topics related to pedagogy in writing, multiculturalism, and inclusion in special education. He has presented in various international conferences and won as Best Presenter at a conference in Thailand.

DEDICATION

This Dissertation is dedicated to my late father, Romeo V. Sales. May this accomplishment make you proud and serve as an honor to your memory. You have always pushed me to do more and be more. You may not be with us anymore, but you will forever be in our hearts. Each day, I strive to be a better person because of you. You are now with our Almighty Father, and may you Rest in Peace.

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ABSTRACT

The Lived Communication Experiences of Special Education Teachers at Miller County Schools

Major Adviser: Dr. Davide Dall'Agata

This phenomenological study was conducted to shed light on the lived communication experiences of the special education teachers at Miller County Schools. The qualitative approach used unstructured interviews to give a voice to the five respondents. The question prompts were based on the observation of self-contained and inclusive classes, IEP meetings, and parent conferences. Making sense of the lived communicative experiences of the special education teachers, the concept of cognizant-sensitive communication emerged. My inquiry revealed that cognizant-sensitive communication in special education allows for improving students' achievement in case it constitutes the essential basis of all teaching, learning and communication processes. Cognizant-sensitive communication strategies allow appropriate approaches and emphasize the value of equality as conditions necessary to create a full-fledged process of communication, teaching and learning with students with special needs. Teacher-parent communication highlighted the need of understanding, building relationships, and truthful feedback. On the other hand, the inside and outside the classroom communication challenges revealed five themes, namely: misunderstanding; behavioral issues; lack of response; unclear understanding of the children's special needs, and struggle to adapt to the changes. Recommendations and solutions to the communication challenges outlined the last

two themes consisting of awareness and sensitivity and prioritizing students' interests. Hence, cognizant-sensitive communication was theorized. It refers to the process where the messenger delves deeper into the abilities, thoughts, interests, and even limitations of the receiver to formulate, select, structure, and relay the message. This phenomenon is common among the lived communication experiences of the special education teachers.

Keywords: Cognizant-sensitive communication, special education, inclusive education, awareness, lived communication experiences, Miller County School

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Rationale and Background of the Study

Teaching students with special needs can be challenging. These students require assistance from teachers with specialized knowledge in the field. The goal is not only to teach them the basic academic skills, but to ensure they eventually become independent. Education leaders argue that 'student agency must become the norm, not the exception (Cooper, 2017). The federal Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) guarantees students with disabilities access to fully licensed special educators. Unfortunately, the United States faces shortage in the number of teachers qualified to do the job. In 2019, 44 States reported special education teacher shortages to the federal government (NPR, 2022).

According to the 1990 IDEA law, public schools are required to create an Individualized Education Program (IEP) for each student who is found to be eligible for special education services. IEPs must be designed to meet the unique educational needs of that child in the least restrictive environment appropriate. Hence, some students are placed in self-contained classes, while others may be eligible for inclusive class environments. In a self-contained class, only qualified teachers may be allowed to teach. It further complicates the effort to fill the vacancies. The role of special educators cannot be overstated in helping realize the goals of these laws. They have various responsibilities in making sure students with special needs achieve their dreams and aspirations.

There have been several studies that looked into the role of special education teachers. Takala et al. (2009) delved into the role of special education teachers in Finland, with emphasis on inclusive education. The study focused on the challenges and issues related to these teachers' jobs. It also involved the pedagogical methods used by the teachers. Finally, the study looked into the perceptions of the teachers on what constitutes inclusive education. Results revealed that in Finnish mainstream schools, "special education teachers often work alone and find their work exhausting. The work profile is unlimited, and often no regular support systems exist." It also suggested that the Finnish model of an inclusive special education system could be even more inclusive if it were to go through a moderate reconstruction. Takala, et al. (2009) concluded that "when organizational support is available, guidelines are clearer and the workload is reasonable, future special education teachers will be able to focus on the learning process, on co-operation with educational staff within the schools and on helping students achieve their individual learning goals".

Balatucan et al. (2022) explored the lived experiences of special education teachers in "quaranteaching". The focus was on the experiences of these teachers while teaching the students at the height of the pandemic, including the successes and challenges. The respondents were also asked about their suggestions in improving teaching quality during quarantine. The results revealed that "the education sector should provide full support to the special education teachers in order to ensure that students with additional needs receive high-quality education". It was also suggested that "administrators should devise a strategy and distribute adequate funds to meet the needs of SPED teachers and their students with additional needs". In regards to the strengthening of parent-teacher collaboration, "parents must become more involved in the education of their child".

Sanchez et al. (2021) also explored the lived experiences of inclusive education teachers who handled students with intellectual disability. The researchers employed a mixed method in obtaining the necessary data. The study focused on the stressors, coping mechanism, fulfilling experiences, and opportunities of the inclusive education teachers. The results revealed that the teachers' main stressors are the students' behavioral issues. The teachers coped using cognitive, social and physical coping resources. Among the themes generated in the study are positing transformations, understanding of the child through team teaching, and salary augmentation. The respondents also suggested that the teachers be equipped with pedagogical knowledge to handle students with behavioral issues through relevant trainings.

Epps, T. (2016) looked into the lived experiences of special education teachers in the implementation of iPad as an instructional tool for students with intellectual disabilities. The researcher used face-to-face interviews, observations, and focus groups to gather the data. The themes revealed in the qualitative data analysis were desire for knowledge, desire for support and guidance, supportive educational advantages, and teaching through challenges.

Special education teachers are also expected not only to teach the students, but to create IEPs, communicate with various stakeholders, and assess student progress. It also includes communication with parents. Kraft & Dougherty (2013) analyzed the effect of teacher-family communication on student engagement using a randomized field experiment. The study revealed that "frequent teacher-family communication immediately increased student engagement as measured by homework completion rates, on-task behavior, and class participation. On average, teacher-family communication increased the odds that students completed their

homework by 40%, decreased instances in which teachers had to redirect students' attention to the task at hand by 25%, and increased class participation rates by 15%".

The cited researches revealed the role of special education teachers across various teaching platforms and philosophies. Some studies have also considered the perceptions of the teachers on inclusive education and the use of various tools in teaching students with special needs. The studies focused mostly on the lived experiences of the teachers in a class environment. However, these studies did not delve deeper into the relationship of the special education teachers and the parents of students with special needs. Furthermore, the role of these teachers in parental communication along with the challenges faced are yet to be studied using a qualitative approach.

Hence, it was worth looking into the lives and experiences of the special education teachers to determine what it is like to teach and communicate to students with special needs. It was also worth looking at the role of the teachers in communicating with parents of students with special needs along with the communication challenges experienced inside and outside the classroom.

This research utilized the phenomenological approach in understanding the essence of the experiences. Phenomenology is commonly described as the study of phenomena as they manifest in our experience, of the way we perceive and understand phenomena, and of the meaning phenomena have in our subjective experience. Vagle (2014) described phenomenology as a reflective and inductive methodology. Phenomenological research methods involve garnering insight into a person's past, lived experiences as they recollect them. Teachers currently employed in schools for the purpose of teaching students with special needs have a unique insight into this area. They spend several hours a day attending to the needs of these

students. They also extend time to meet with parents to create and modify an IEP, and follow up on the progress of the students. Hence, it is worth looking into their lived experiences. Themes generated from the data obtained from the respondents were used in answering the research questions.

Research Question and Objectives

The research aimed to answer the research question, “*What are the lived communication experiences of the special education teachers at Miller County Schools?*” This study aimed to understand the lived communication experiences of the special education teachers at Miller County Schools to determine what it is like to do the job. The research looked at the teaching, learning, and communication processes in the class, and how the results are communicated to the parents, and determined the essence of special education teaching.

Specifically, this research aimed to:

1. Understand what teaching and communicating with students who have special needs means;
2. Comprehend the role of the teachers in communicating with parents of students with special needs;
3. Determine the communication challenges experienced inside and outside the classroom; and
4. Identify the difficulties in finding qualified special education teachers.

Significance of the Study and Contributions

The results of this study revealed the reality in the lives of the special education teachers and what they experience in the conduct of their duties within the classroom and beyond. Hence, the study is significant since it will provide the Miller County School Systems with a clear picture on the challenges experienced by the teachers and suggestions in solving them. It includes the challenges faced while teaching and communicating to students with special needs and communicating with the parents.

It is also of great significance to the improvement of the pedagogy in special education. The lived experiences of the teachers could reveal the best practices used in class, including the tools and devices to boost the students' learning abilities.

The parents of students with special needs and other members of the IEP teams may also benefit from this research. The results may determine ways to improve the communication process and allow various stakeholders to create and modify a quality IEP that meets the students' needs and ensure that it is implemented. Communicating the results will also be improved as a result of this research.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of this study included the teaching and communication experiences of the respondents along with their experiences in meeting with parents for IEP creation, modification, and progress follow-up. It did not only include the potential changes in the students' current educational experience, but also their transition to life outside the school.

This study only included certified special education teachers at Miller County Middle School or Miller County High School, with at least two years of teaching students with special needs (self-contained or inclusive teaching environments). The respondents also have an experience in writing IEPs or joining IEP meetings, including

communication with parents of students with special needs. The teachers consented to the recording of the interview before participating in the research.

This study had a few limitations. First, it was conducted in a small rural school in the State of Georgia and may not reflect the challenges faced by special education teachers in big cities with a huge student population. Second, the IEP follow-up meetings only happened upon the request of the parents. The research did not emphasize on parental communication during the IEP modification since scheduling was contingent upon the parents. Finally, the conclusions reached in this study were only based upon the responses of a limited set of respondents. In this research, there were five (5) respondents. Therefore, the researcher must do his best in the interview phase to present the data and communicate what the data reveals given the purpose of the study (Patton, 2002).

Operational Definition of Terminologies

This section introduces various terms used in the study based on how they were specifically used in the context of the research.

504 Plan - It is a plan developed to ensure that a child who has a disability identified under the law and is attending an elementary or secondary educational institution receives accommodations that will ensure their academic success and access to the learning environment.

Accommodations- An alteration of environment, curriculum format, or equipment that allows an individual with a disability to gain access to content and/or complete assigned tasks.

Alternative school - Miller County School Systems utilize an alternative school to further the education of students with behavioral issues, especially after breaking a behavioral contract signed by the students and parents.

Assistive technology - Assistive technology (AT) is any item, piece of equipment, software program, or product system that is used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of persons with disabilities. In Miller County, it may include a Chromebook, adjustable seats, mobile devices, and audiobooks.

Distance learning - It is a way of educating students online. Lectures and learning materials are sent over the internet. Students work from home, not in a classroom. During the Covid-19 pandemic, all Miller County students continued their education through this method, including students with special needs. For academic year 2022, students at risk of getting ill when placed in a regular school environment continued distance education.

IEP - An Individualized Education Program (IEP) is a written education plan designed to meet a child's learning needs. All students diagnosed with special needs at Miller County have an IEP and a case manager. Parents meet with the other members of the IEP team to create and modify the IEP, including additional meetings if deemed necessary.

IEP Meeting- The purpose of IEP meetings is to discuss, develop, and review a student's IEP. Every year, schools are required to hold an IEP meeting to review students' progress. However, parents have the right to call an IEP meeting anytime for specific issues.

Inclusive classrooms - Typically, inclusive classrooms refer to a class environment that includes students with special needs, impairments, or disabilities only. Sometimes inclusive classrooms can refer to taking the initiative to ensure that

the classroom includes people of diverse races, economic backgrounds, varying cultures, and sexual orientations. In Miller County, students with special needs may be placed in an inclusive class if the IEP team, including the parents, consent to it. The student may join students without special needs in one or more classes.

Parent conference- It refers to a short meeting or conference between the parents and teachers of students to discuss a child's progress at school and find solutions to academic or behavioral problems.

Self-contained classes- It refers to a classroom where the special education teacher is responsible for the instruction of all academic subjects.

Special education - It refers to the practice of educating students in a way that accommodates their individual differences, disabilities, and special needs. Miller County Schools adhere to federal and state laws governing the education of students with special needs, and ensure their rights are met and respected.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter provides a collection of researches and literature related to the study. It provides detailed definitions of terms based on the context of the study. Finally, it discusses useful underpinning theories.

Special Education Laws in the United States

Special education in the United States has drastically evolved over the years. Back then, schools catered to specific individuals. The first American schools to serve those with disabilities were established in the 1800s, and they too were private but sometimes served more of a charitable purpose than an educational one (National Disability Authority). Over time, laws have been passed to provide for the needs of students with disabilities. One of the most significant laws is "*The Education For All Handicapped Children Act*" (EHA), that was signed into law by President Ford in 1975. According to govtrack.us, the law was passed with these goals:

- To ensure that special education services are available to children who need them;
- To guarantee that decisions about services to students with disabilities are fair and appropriate;
- To establish specific management and auditing requirements for special education, and
- To provide federal funds to help the states educate students with disabilities.

The Education of All Handicapped Children Act was passed in 1975, and in 1990, amendments to the law were passed, effectively changing the name to IDEA or Individuals with Disabilities Education Act. In 1997 and again in 2004, additional amendments were passed to ensure equal access to education.

With the passage of the law, children from 13 categories of disabilities were now entitled to a special education process that encompassed the six provisions.

According to Lee, A. IDEA places two big responsibilities on states and their public schools. First, school districts must provide a free appropriate public education (FAPE) to kids with disabilities. And these kids must learn side by side with peers as much as possible. They have to be in a Least Restrictive Environment (LRE). Schools must find and evaluate students who may have disabilities, at no cost to families or “Child Find”. If a child has a qualifying disability, schools must offer special education and related services (like speech therapy and counseling) to meet the child’s unique needs. An Individualized Education Program (IEP) is also necessary.

Another goal of the IDEA law is to require schools to give parents a voice in their child’s education. At every point in the process, IDEA gives parents specific rights and protections, also called procedural safeguards. While IDEA covers public schools, it also affects public magnet and charter schools, and to a certain extent, private schools. The law also provides early intervention services to infants and toddlers up to age 3.

The Assistive Technology Act of 1998 (re-authorized in 2004) is another critical law. The law grants to states to maintain comprehensive statewide programs designed to: (1) maximize the ability of individuals with disabilities, and their family members, guardians, advocates, and authorized representatives, to obtain AT; and (2) increase access to AT.

The act also requires States to use portions of AT grant funds for: (1) State-level activities, including State financing system activities (which may include loan programs) to increase access to and funding for AT devices and services, as well as for programs for device reutilization, device loan, and device demonstration and information; and (2) State leadership activities, including training and technical, public-awareness activities, and coordination and collaboration (<https://www.congress.gov/bill/108th-congress/house-bill/4278>. H.R.4278 - Assistive Technology Act of 2004).

Individualized Educational Program (IEP)

The Individuals with Disabilities Education Improvement Act (IDEA, 2004) mandates parent participation in *individualized education program* (IEP) teams and decisions (20 U.S.C. 614 (e)). The IEP sets out goals that the child will work towards during the year. It lists the services the school system has committed to provide to help achieve these goals. It also explains how the school will track progress towards reaching these goals and how that progress will be reported to the parents. Congress noted that the education of children with disabilities improved by “strengthening the role and responsibility of parents and ensuring that families of such children have meaningful opportunities to participate in the education of their children at school and at home” (20 U.S.C. 1400 (c) (5) and (d)).

IEPs must be written at least annually. Typically, IEP meetings are held in the spring, at which time the next year’s IEP is written. However, this is not the only time that an IEP meeting may be held. Parents or school personnel should request an IEP meeting whenever they believe that the IEP needs to be reviewed or revised. The child’s IEP team must revise IEP to address any lack of expected progress toward her

annual goals and in the general education curriculum (Alabama Disabilities Advocacy Program, 2014). The IEP does not only cover the activities during the school year, but also a transition plan for the accomplishment of long-term goals. IEP meetings involve the school representatives, parents, and special education experts. Parent and school collaboration may take many forms, including home-school communication notebooks (Kurth et al., 2018) and regular conversations (e.g., Haines, Gross, Blue-Banning, Francis, & Turnbull, 2015). Parent input in making decisions is particularly necessary for students with the most significant support needs, defined as students who have extensive and pervasive support needs across domains (e.g., communication, cognition, mobility) who will need a myriad of supports to meet their existing support needs and to attain their educational and post-educational goals (Spooner, Knight, Browder, & Smith, 2012).

Active participation in IEP meetings is associated with a myriad of benefits, including increased academic achievement (Barnard-Brak & Lechtenberger, 2010). Participation can provide an opportunity for students to engage in their academic planning while developing and practicing self-determination skills (Williams-Diehm et al., 2008). If parents have strong partnership with the school team and positive experiences at IEP meetings, student involvement may also be more likely (deFur, 2012).

Assistive Technology in Special Education

The *Technology Related Assistance for Individuals with Disabilities Act* (P.L. 100-407) increased access to, availability of, and funding for assistive technology for all individuals with disabilities, including very young children. The Act was amended in

1994 (P.L. 103-218). In 1998 Congress enacted the Assistive Technology Act (P.L. 105-394) and in 2004, the AT Act was amended.

The term "*assistive technology service*" means any service that directly assists a child with a disability in the selection, acquisition, or use of an assistive technology device. It includes the evaluation of the needs of such child, including a functional evaluation of the child in the child's customary environment; purchasing, leasing, or otherwise providing for the acquisition of assistive technology devices by such child; selecting, designing, fitting, customizing, adapting, applying, maintaining, repairing, or replacing assistive technology devices; coordinating and using other therapies, interventions, or services with assistive technology devices, such as those associated with existing education and rehabilitation plans and programs; training or technical assistance for such child, or, where appropriate, the family of such child; and training or technical assistance for professionals (including individuals providing education and rehabilitation services), employers, or other individuals who provide services to, employ, or are otherwise substantially involved in the major life functions of such child". (The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (2004). 20 U.S.C. 1401(2))

McCray, Brownell, and Lignugaris (2014) reported that most special educators do not have the knowledge to select, evaluate, and suggest assistive technology to students with special needs. The findings of the studies are worrying and there is a need to emphasize on the training of assistive technology in the preparation of special teachers. According to Beard, Carpenter, and Johnson (2011), it is a challenging task. Although many efforts have been made to raise awareness of assistive technology, competencies in assistive technology still lack assistive technology knowledge and skills (Judge & Sims, 2009; Lee & Vega, 2005; Long, Wolverton, Perry & Thomas, 2007).

The study by Wong & Cohen (2013) is significant as it examines the use of assistive technology by visually impaired students and their teachers. While teachers claimed to be comfortable with low and medium technologies, many described themselves as "illiterate", referring to high-tech assistive technology devices. Research by Flanagan, Bock, and Richardson (2013) examined special education teachers' use and perceptions of assistive technology (AT) and the effects of assistive technology use in a content area for students with high incidence disabilities. They concluded that the mode for teacher-reported use of low- and high-tech assistive technology was less than once per week.

Maurya and Singh (2021) argued that the indifference seen in the awareness of both the new assistive technologies and the existent assistive technology in the past by the special educators have been replaced by the acceptance for the new and the technology. They also concluded that in order to achieve the ultimate results of education, teachers have realized that they must recognize that every aspect of adult life, regardless of disability, implies the use of assistive technologies.

Special Education During Covid-19 Pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic has drastically impacted people's lives in many ways. It includes financial to social interactions, family affairs, business relations, physical and mental health. It is even more pronounced in the field of education. According to UNESCO, the COVID-19 pandemic has been the worst shock to education systems in a century, with more than 1.6 billion children and youth not being able to attend school for months. Furthermore, parents of students with special needs encountered considerable difficulty in supporting their children's online learning (Azoulay, 2020). Depending on the students' unique needs, individual services are given through individualized education programs (IEP) in hope to have a long-lasting impact to their education exposure (Hartmann, 2016).

It was revealed in the study of Parmigiani et al. (2020) that most of the class and special education teachers affirmed that they were not prepared to create online inclusive activities, and in fact, they would have needed to follow specific courses. In regard to academic support, about 7 in 10 Latino and Black parents are concerned they do not have the resources or supplies to help their child stay academically on track (The Education Trust, 2020).

Apart from regular instruction, the pandemic also affected the assessment of students with special needs. Elion, L. as cited by Nelson, A. (2020) said that special education assessments are starting to take place remotely, but that is hardly a comfort for parents. Standardized assessments were not designed and normed for remote delivery and IEP teams are now relying, at least partially, on data gathered by parents to inform decisions. With the willingness of the teachers to adjust to meet the demands, students with special needs continued receiving services. Special education teachers

deliver special education services through each student's IEP resulting in them being able to make progress (Turnbell, H., Turnbell, A., Wehmeyer, & Park, 2003).

Teaching students with special needs under regular circumstances is already challenging. The pandemic has only exacerbated the challenges teachers face. While distance learning became an alternative, it did not necessarily address the students' needs. In the study of Davis, K. (2021), it was revealed that with this delivery method of education, distance learning can be ideal/beneficial for some students who are independent learners; but, for most students, distance learning has been the most difficult source for continuing education.

Inclusive Education

According to UNICEF (2010), inclusion is really about how well child-friendly schools are doing at making practical changes so that all children, regardless of their background or ability to succeed. Inclusive education is a process as well as a practice of removing barriers and enabling all students, including previously excluded groups, to learn and participate effectively within general school systems (Wanjohi, 2010).

The scope of inclusive education goes far beyond learners with disabilities and has now been extended to cover all learners with special educational needs, whatever their origins (Mitchell, 2015). It provides better opportunities for learning within the individual differences (Fernandes, 2010). Motivation is also enhanced in an inclusive classroom environment. Children with varying abilities are often better motivated when they learn in classes surrounded by other children (Manichander, 2015). It also helps in reducing the effects of inferiority complex on the part of the exceptional persons.

Thereby leading a healthy completion with the normal persons, resulting in high academic achievement (Olusegun, 2007).

Historically, inclusive education emerged as a result of this clarion call made on the international community by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) to give each child the opportunity to achieve and maintain an acceptable level of learning. The idea is to provide everyone a chance to succeed and be viewed equally. As Bruner (2002) points out, a child with one arm or leg who cannot lead a normal life outside of school is not considered disabled in a school where a barrier-free environment adapted to his physical characteristics is created. The more complete the isolation, the less aware society becomes of the needs of such a child and of the barriers that prevent him from fully communicating with other members of the society (Beirne-Smith, 2018).

The success of inclusion in classrooms also depends on the attitude of the teachers. Research has shown that when teachers have positive mindsets toward inclusion, they more readily adapt their teaching methods to meet a variety of student learning needs (Cullen, Gregory, & Noto, 2010). Successful implementation of inclusive practices depends mainly on teachers' attitudes towards children with special needs and their inclusion, and teachers' willingness to work with children with special needs in their classrooms (Rakap, Cig, & Parlak-Rakap, 2017).

American concepts of inclusive education are united by the idea that creating an inclusive educational environment affects not only the reform of the educational system but also the rethinking of the philosophy of education based on the ideas of freedom, justice and equality.

Inclusion also benefits non-disabled peers. Kent-Walsh and Light (2003) and Soto et al. (2001) found that classmates were more aware and accepting of students with special needs, viewing them as more capable and “normal.” Students without disabilities provide appropriate role models for their peers with disabilities and can become responsive to their communication efforts (Soto et al., 2001). Challenges include limited resources, time challenges, instructional styles, modification of curricular materials, and negative attitudes and perceptions toward students with disabilities (Calculator, 2009; Downing, 2005; Kramlich, 2012).

Perception on Inclusive Education

Mainstream teacher attitude had become a major barrier to the inclusion of these students. Some teachers view inclusive education in a negative light. Avramidis and Norwich (2002) reviewed several studies and found that teachers regarded children with emotional and behavioral difficulties as the most difficult to include. McGregor and Campbell (2001) found that the unpredictable nature of young children with autism has the potential to cause extreme confusion and distress with general education teachers.

Sam, K. et al, 2015 argued that the lack of pre-service teacher training for inclusive settings, as cited by the teachers, is an important consideration for training providers. Sharma, Ee, & Desai (2003) also found that training in special education appeared to lessen pre-service teacher’s concerns regarding inclusive education. Inclusive education programme could be successfully implemented if the level of the teachers’ competency is increased. Thus, the opportunities to attend courses that are related to the inclusive education program have to be created, especially for those who lack of exposure and training in special education (Ali, et al., 2006).

Not everyone shares the same negative view towards inclusive education. Ali, Mustapha, and Jelas (2006) found that in general, teachers held positive attitudes towards inclusive education. According to the results of their study, the teachers agreed that inclusive education enhanced social interaction and inclusion among the students and thus minimizing negative stereotypes on special needs students. Research also shows that high educational status and quality of training in special education resulted in more positivity in the attitudes of teachers towards inclusive education in the mainstream classroom (Costello & Boyle, 2013). Ruwandi (2012) says, inclusive education means embracing everyone and making a commitment to provide every student with a community, every citizen with a democracy and the undeniable right to belong.

Several factors also contribute to the success of inclusive classes and how teachers perceive them. Collaboration decision making between general education classes and special education teachers based on careful consideration of the individual's learning goals and the typical classroom practices is advocated to facilitate contextualization of the individual plan within the general education curriculum (Bhroin & King, 2020). Providing teachers with the right tools can also boost a more positive perception. According to Khursheed et al., 2020, among the reasons elementary teachers usually have a negative attitude towards inclusive education, because they have a lack of training and facilities are not available to teachers. The same research also revealed the same concerns among high school teachers. They indicated that they were not well prepared and there was fewer training offered to prepare them for inclusion. Teacher training has become a fundamental pillar of the quality of the educational response of students and the generation of attitudes and positive predisposition towards inclusion (Pérez-Jorge et al., 2021). Teachers must be aware

of the fact that education and training systems can increase their capacity to include all earners and to achieve equitable outcomes for all, while meeting the increasing diversity of learners' needs, maintaining cultural diversity and improving quality of inclusive education (Marin, 2014). Ultimately, a change in attitude towards inclusion can boost teachers' perception. Reform is highly dependent on the ability to change conservative ideas that many teachers, all over the world hold in relation to teaching and learning (Orion & Thompson, 1999). Positive perceptions of teachers are deemed to be necessary and indeed an important starting point for the development of a suitable inclusive school environment (Leung & Mak, 2010; Parasuram, 2006).

Communicating to Students with Special Needs

Communication is both a basic need and a basic right of all human beings (American Speech-Language-Hearing Association, 2014; United Nations, 2008). All persons do communicate in some way; however, the effectiveness and efficiency of this communication vary with a number of individual and environmental factors. Downing and Flavey (2015) state that the assumption that all people communicate is appropriate in that it errors on the side of inclusiveness and respect for all individuals.

An adult with severe disability who shows signs of irritation, moving her head back and forth when offered an object, can be understood by a competent communicative partner as protesting even if her behavior does not meet accepted criteria for communicative intent (Bates, 1976). Tools, such as a cultural competence checklist (ASHA, 2010), may be used to determine whether service delivery addresses the needs of individuals from diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds. For individuals with severe intellectual disabilities and autism, early intensive behavioral

intervention has been particularly successful in establishing initial communication repertoires (Howard, et al 2005; Warren et al., 2011)

Communication intervention is necessary to help students with special needs. Brady, et al. (2016) defined communication intervention as “any systematic effort to improve how individuals understand the communication of others and express themselves.” Furthermore, Brady, et al (2016) suggested that other emerging intervention trends, including a more expansive view of who intervenes, what to target, where intervention occurs, and how to measure progress.

There are various devices that may help with the communication process. Speech-generating devices or SGDs are portable communication systems that provide either synthetic or recorded voice output. Some evidence indicates that voice feedback offered through SGDs may support literacy-skills development (Blischak, Lombardino, & Dyson, 2003; Brady, 2000). Visual scene displays utilize photographs or images of familiar scenes, objects, or people displayed on a tablet, touch-screen computer, or dynamic-display device. A learner can touch a hot spot on the picture to communicate a message related to the scene. Teachers can utilize various strategies to boost the communication process.

Communicating to students with special needs also requires practice. Teaching and refining communication skills must include explicit teaching for how a student is to communicate a message (Beukelman & Mirenda, 2013). It is also essential to offer students a wait time as they are unable to respond immediately. In general, learners with severe disabilities need additional time to respond to verbal and non-verbal input (Johnson & Parker, 2013). There will be challenges that come in communicating to students with special needs and it is imperative that teachers handling them possess the right skills and attitudes to get the job done.

Communicating with Parents of Students with Special Needs

Raising children with special needs can be challenging. Cantwell et al. (2014) revealed that these parents have an increased feelings of pessimism about the future. Socially, there is the possibility of losing friends and social contacts because it may be difficult to spend time away from the child, along with people's tendency to distance themselves from those who are 'different' (McCubbin & Patterson 1983; Portowitz & Rimmerman 1985). Parents of a child with special needs find themselves facing a coping process accompanied by thoughts of their child's unclear future (Duvdevany, 2000; Cantwell et al., 2014). For discussions between parents and students to affect the child's education, parents need detailed knowledge of school processes and effective learning methods, and they must be able to use that knowledge in discussion with their children (Park, 2008).

There are many other factors which can be a predictor of stress in parents, like low level of mother's education, fathers' poor health, poverty and less social support. Parents' interpersonal relationship, their financial adjustments and their professional growth together influence their adjustment in terms of handling their special needs child. Some studies found that the presence of social support significantly predicts the individual's ability to cope with stress and it was knowing that they are valued by others is an important psychological factor in helping them to forget the negative aspects of their lives, and thinking more positively about their environment.

Technology also plays a crucial role in the success of the teacher-parent communication. For discussions between parents and students to affect the child's education, parents need detailed knowledge of school processes and effective learning methods, and they must be able to use that knowledge in discussion with their children (Park, 2008). Using technology, such as e-mail, to communicate from school

to home can be a positive and rewarding experience (Tobolka, 2006). However, not all parents have access to appropriate technology to communicate. The “digital divide” refers to the gap between households, businesses, and geographical areas based on the socioeconomic status and their opportunity to access information through different technological communication systems (Koss, 2001). Teachers have to consider this issue in its efforts to communicate with parents.

The issues related to parental communication begin even before the child is officially diagnosed. Some parents deny the possibility of their children having special needs. Parents are most often not mental-health experts, but they are experts in knowing their children (Eicher, 2018). Therefore, telling them to have their child diagnosed could be met with hesitation. Even when the child receives an official diagnosis, the problem does not end. Eicher (2018) also argued that parents new to the individualized education program (IEP) process are then confused and angry. Worse yet, some parents accept the initial denial, and then the child does not receive an evaluation. For this reason, special education teachers have to be careful in addressing these parents. According to the Texas Department of Family and Protective Services, teachers have to possess the following qualities during the interaction with parents: honest, respectful, timely, constructive, and reciprocal.

Interpretative and Interaction Theories of Communication

The underpinning research used in this study is the interpretative and interaction theories of communication. All forms of communications are grounded on meaning and interaction. Interpretative and interaction theories state that how people express their social situation and how these effects bring about a change in their lives.

The Interactional approach of Paul Watzlawick is involved in an interpersonal type of communication. Watzlawick's theory as cited by Nicdao (2019) is grounded on the five suppositions. First, people are always communicating. This means that even if we remain silent or we prefer not to utter a word, or not do anything, we are still and always communicating. We never stop communicating. Gestures, facial expressions and other body movements make up a great part of the communication process. The theory also suggests that people communicate using both digital and analogical methods. Digital communication may refer to objects by name. Language is considered to be digital. Analogical methods consider objects by likeness. Non-verbal communication is considered analogical.

Furthermore, communication is equivalent to content and relationship. Content is the purpose, the message, the aim of the source in starting the communication process, while relationship is the manner in which this purpose has been conveyed. The fourth supposition is that the quality of the relationship is based on the manner in which communication participants deal with the communication flow. As people communicate, the sender and receiver interpret the message sent and received in different ways. And the interpretation they give to the message depends largely on their culture, behavior and beliefs in life. Finally, communication can be complementary or symmetrical. Complementary type of communication means communication participants have diverse power. On the other hand, symmetrical type of communication means communication participants have equal power.

This theory was used in this research since it looks into the dynamic relationship of the people involved in the communicative process. The nature of the relationship is also given attention in this theory. The culture and behavior during the communicative process might also impact the sender's ability to send the message

and the recipient's interpretation of it. Since the study dives into the essence of the lived communication experiences of the special needs teachers, exploring various factors that might affect the process would be appropriate.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach

There is an increasing acknowledgement of a need for multiple research methodologies in special education (Odom, et. al., 2005). It allows for the deeper understanding of the issues and concepts surrounding the subject. This research followed a qualitative approach. It allowed the researcher to delve deeper into the lived experiences of the teachers and shed light on the nuances of teaching students with special needs along with the ways of communicating with their parents. While previous quantitative studies are available in regards to this field, they were not enough to delve deeper into what every teacher has gone through while practicing the profession.

This study looked at the teaching, learning, and communicating processes in the class and how the results are communicated with the parents. The study involved teachers in the United States, where different laws and guidelines covering special education, including teacher certification apply. Understanding what teaching means and what parental communication is like, can only be captured using a qualitative approach. The nuances were highlighted through the phenomenological research, including the specific emotions of the teachers. The approach also helped make meaning out of these experiences and use it to improve special education in the school system, and to a certain extent, the United States of America.

This study used the phenomenological approach in qualitative research. Phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013).

An accurate presentation of the experience under study is more important in this approach than the ability to claim that the findings apply to across situations or people (Boss et al., 1996). The emphasis on accurately portraying the phenomenon means that large numbers of participants are not required. The goal is to gather descriptions of their lived experience which are rich in detail and imagery, as well as reflection on its theological or psychological meaning. The likelihood of achieving this goal can be enhanced by using a purposeful sample.

Interviews are by far the most common means of gathering data, although one might also use written texts, such as prayers written in open prayer books in hospital chapels, for example (Grossoehme, 2014); ap Sion, 2013; Grossoehme, 1996). The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994): What have you experienced in terms of the phenomenon? What contexts or situation have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013)?

Phenomenological researches consist of several steps. According to Giorgi (1985), it starts with the immersion in the data. It involves reading and re-reading of the transcribed interviews and listening to the recorded interviews to hear the tone and timbre of the voices. Second, the texts are coded, in which the words, phrases or sentences that stand out as describing the experience or phenomena under study, or which express outright its meaning for the participant are extracted or highlighted. Third, similar meaning units are placed into categories. Fourth, for each meaning unit the meaning of the participants' own words is spelled out. Finally, each of the transformed statements of meaning are combined into a few thematic statements that describe the experience (Grossoehme, 2014; Bassett, 2004; Boss, et. Al 1996).

This approach was used as the foundation for this research since the goal is to understand the essence of communication involving special education teachers and

students with special needs; and special education teachers and parents of students with special needs. Interview was used in gathering information from the respondents. Class observations helped in formulating the interview questions. The phenomenological approach also works by purposefully selecting the respondents. In this research, only the special education teachers at Miller County Schools were included. Ultimately, the interpretation of the interview results were to answer the research questions.

The underlying theory that helped shape the research is the Interpretative and Interactive Theory of Interpersonal Communication. According to Nicdao (2019), meaning and interaction constitute the communication process. All types of communication are grounded on meaning and interaction, which, at the same time, are closely intertwined. Nicdao (2019) added that the Interpretative and Interaction theories consider communication as a process of dynamic interchange through which individuals interact with other individuals, interpreting, sharing and defining their perception of reality by means of this interaction.

Paul Watzlawick's study on interaction elucidates how communication is stimulated during an interpersonal communication. He classified five axioms which are widely recognized as interactional view. These are the axioms which describe how misinterpretation can occur in a communication process.

First, he believes that people can involve in long conversations and in some cases a non-verbal gesture or even silence can be regarded as communication. This implies that whether you are communicating verbally or non-verbally the receiver will consider it as a communication.

It is also a part of his believe that the speaker will use different ways of communication for different people. Relationships play a vital role in the

communication process. A person's communication varies according to difference in relationships.

Third, the nature of the relationship depends on the punctuation of the communication sequence. In a communication process, the sender and the receiver interpret the message differently according to their behavior.

Fourth, the nonverbal communication and other gestures which are interpreted as messages similar to the first axiom and also the digital content used in the communication process are being described in this axiom.

Finally, all communication is symmetrical or complementary. Relational interaction among the components such as symmetrical interchange and complementary interchange can be seen in this axiom. Symmetrical interaction means the communication is grounded on equal powers while complementary interaction holds that communications have differences in power.

Since the respondents of the research came from different cultural backgrounds and have varied life experiences, seeing them through the lens of this theory helped better understand the communicative practices involved. It also helped make meaning to the responses based on the interactions in various settings. The special education teachers as the respondents of the study shared their perception of reality based on their interactions with special needs students and their parents.

The phenomenological approach looked into the meanings of these interactions from the lived experiences of the special education teachers. Apart from interviews, the researcher also looked at the class interactions and IEP meetings to further the understanding of the teachers' lived communication experiences.

Period and Site of the Study

The study was conducted from December 2022 to January 2023 at Miller County Schools. The school system is located at Colquitt, Georgia, USA. The school serves as the only public school in the county.

Figure 1

Location of the Study Area

Google Maps. Retrieved November 7, 2022. <https://goo.gl/maps/aB7GPBKUNL6TMhvF7>

The campus at 996 Phillipsburg Road, Colquitt, Georgia hosts the elementary, middle, and high schools. Below is the student and teacher population of the Miller County Schools as of the school year 2022.

Table 1

Miller County Schools Population

Miller County Schools	Students	Teachers
Elementary	346	23
Middle	176	14
High	255	17

Research Participants

The study used the purposive sampling technique and the participants were identified using these inclusion criteria:

1. A certified special education teacher at Miller County Middle School or Miller County High School.
2. An experienced teacher who has been teaching at the school for at least two years.
3. Is currently handling or has taught students in self-contained and inclusive teaching environments.
4. Has communicated with parents of students with special needs or has been involved in an IEP meeting.

The researcher interviewed five (5) certified special education teachers from the Miller County Schools.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations play a fundamental role in qualitative research. The ethical integrity of the research is under the responsibility of the researcher and is undissociated from its scientific quality. Ethical issues are present in the entire trajectory, from the selection of the object, going on to the definition of the theoretical

bases, objectives, methodological framework, and continuing into the interpretation and dissemination of outcomes, whether to the researched persons, scientific community, managers or the entire society (Webster, et al., 2014). Hence, the researcher ensured the ethical conduct of the study and constantly favored the well-being of the research participants.

Some important ethical concerns that should be taken into account while carrying out qualitative research are: anonymity, confidentiality and informed consent (Richards, H.M., 2022). For qualitative researchers, it is of the utmost importance to specify in advance which data will be collected and how they are to be used (Hoeyer, K., et al, 2005). The respondents for this research were special education teachers whose classes and interactions with parents and students were observed. The consent of all the involved parties was requested and they were informed about how the collected data will be used. Confidentiality was observed and the recorded information was used for the purpose of this research. The identity of the respondents was not revealed in any of the components during the publication of the results, and aliases were used to hide the true identity of the respondents.

The research also aimed to reduce the risks of biases. According to Bos, J. (2020), these biases include (among others): publication bias (non-publication of null results), confirmation bias (tendency to look for confirmative results, disregarding of contradictory information), and funding bias (tendency to support the study's financial supporter).

This research was performed in accordance with the guidelines of The Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act. It is a federal law that protects the privacy of student education records. The law applies to all schools that receive funds under an

applicable program of the U.S. Department of Education. The researcher followed the guidelines enclosed under this federal law.

Research Design

This study focused on the lived communication experiences of special education teachers at Miller County Schools, Georgia, USA. For this study, I chose observations and interviews because I believe these methods provided an opportunity to clearly observe what occurs during the communication acts. The combination of observations and interviews allowed me to wholly assess the perspectives of special education teachers and their interactions, communications, and reactions instead of solely the reports of their experiences.

Unstructured interview was used as the primary method in data collection. Unstructured interviews are the most popular interview method in phenomenological research (Vagle, 2014). Unstructured interview resembles a conversation more than an interview and is always thought to be a “controlled conversation,” which is skewed towards the interests of the interviewer (Gray, 2009). Observation was also utilized to further understand the communicative practices of the teachers when dealing with the students in both self-contained and inclusive classes. The observation was also critical in forming the relevant questions asked during the interviews. The observations were done in classrooms, IEP meetings, and parent conferences.

The interview questions were divided into the following categories: a) communication strategies with students with special needs; b) communication strategies with the parents of students with special needs; c) communication challenges in self-contained and inclusive classes; d) communication during the pandemic, and e) recommendations/solutions to the identified challenges. While these

were the main points of discussions, follow-up questions were added as deemed necessary to extract the essence of the respondents' lived communication experiences.

The responses were recorded through audio format, and in accordance with the guidelines of The Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act. According to the law, "As with any other "education record," a photo or video of a student is an education record, subject to specific exclusions, when the photo or video is: (1) directly related to a student; and (2) maintained by an educational agency or institution or by a party acting for the agency or institution." This student privacy law prevents the researcher from recording the class observation.

After the conversation, the recorded interview was transcribed. After transcription, the researcher used thematic coding. It is a form of qualitative analysis which involves recording or identifying passages of text or images that are linked by a common theme or idea to index the text into categories and therefore establish a "framework of thematic ideas about it" (Gibbs, 2007).

Data Collection Instruments and Procedure

The first step was to request for the approval of the Principal and the Special Education Director to conduct the research. A letter was given to them requesting the conduct of this study and explaining the nature of the research. Upon approval of the request, the researcher conducted class observations, which were done prior to the interviews to help formulate appropriate questions. At least one observation per teacher was conducted. These observations provided the researcher with better insights into what these teachers go through in the class. The researcher also observed at least one IEP meeting and one parent conference based on the respondents' caseload.

Lack of Response

As established by the respondents, their responsibilities do not end inside the class. They also have to communicate with the parents, and it comes with challenges. A common issue is making them answer the calls or respond to emails. The respondents identified potential reasons for the lack of communication, including how busy the parents are. S-23-1 said that there were multiple instances where parents received a call, but failed to answer. H-24-2 also discussed how some emails go unanswered, including notes sent home. M-21-3 believes that it depends on the parents. Some parents hate being bothered, *"...but then again, I have some parents that I can pick my phone at any one point in time, and they are going to pick up their phone on the spot."* The respondents discussed the level of investment the parents have on their children's education. Some are more invested than the others. When these parents care about their children's future, communicating with them is easier.

M-7-5 discussed the possibility that some parents do not respond since they have a lot on their plates. They have to work hard and raise several children. Hence, they are unable to pay attention to their special needs child. Poverty was also another potential reason. Some families do not even have phones at home that teachers can contact. The differences in these parents' socio-economic background affect accessibility. A-21-4 said that the mode of communication might also be a factor. *"Some parents prefer text over phone calls. They might respond after receiving a text, but will not answer phone calls."* However, A-21-4 agreed on the impact of the parents' socio-economic status on their ability to respond.

"Some parents don't want to be bothered, and they just don't respond." [M-21-3]

“A lot of parents I deal with don’t like phone calls. They’d rather have text. They might be busy and are unable to answer right away.” [A-21-4]

“They either have no working number or I leave a message and they won’t call back. It’s not all parents, but at least 50%.” [S-23-1]

“Maybe, they’re busy or they think they’re too busy to answer my calls.” [H-24-2]

Unclear Understanding of the Children’s Special Needs

The IDEA law Section 300.111 (Child Find) indicates that children “who are in need of special education and related services, are identified, located, and evaluated.” While many children with special needs receive early diagnosis and given special services, some get diagnosed late. It could be due to the late appearance of visible symptoms or parents in denial about the possibility that their children have special needs. When children receive official diagnosis earlier, parents have a choice of asking for an IEP. Special services are immediately available once the child has an IEP. Parents also become more familiar with their children’s medical issues and physical impairments. The respondents agreed that the cases might be different since some parents know a little about their children’s condition. Hence, it is another challenge they deal with in parental communication.

M-7-5 presented an example about a parent who did not even understand her son’s allergies. *“He was breaking out at school and they sent us a list of all his allergies, and this is what’s going to happen. I went to the lunch room and tell that he can’t have a ham sandwich on wheat bread with cheese because he is allergic to pork,*

dairy, and wheat. And, they (the other teachers) were like, we called his momma, and she said it was fine.” M-7-5 had to explain to the parent what these allergies mean and what the child cannot eat.

M-21-3 cited an example where the parent’s lack of knowledge on how to handle the student’s behavioral issues became a problem at school. *“Well, they don’t have issues as long as you give that child everything he needs to avoid a tantrum... So, when I tell the kid no, we have a major malfunction in the classroom.”* The parents may not have an idea on how to deal with such behavioral problem or are even unaware that their children behave a certain way. S-23-1 also recalled instances when the parents only heard about their children’s behavior at school for the first time during a parent conference. The respondents agreed that this communication challenge makes it harder to plan the path forward for the students as parents have to be active and informed partners.

“...but their parents came from a severely delayed family. She (The mother) sees nothing wrong with her lifestyle and how she thinks. She doesn’t know everything about her child’s condition since she might have one too.” [M-7-5]

“Sometimes, you have to do hard things and report things that you see as a teacher because it’s mandatory. And, the parents get upset and mad since they didn’t know their children’s behavior very well.” [A-21-4]

“So, there’s no behavioral discipline (at home) and it’s left up to the teachers since some parents are unaware.” [M-21-3]

"We have to remind the parents about the possible symptoms of their child's condition to be on the same page when doing the IEP." [S-21-3]

Struggle to Adapt to the Changes

While these challenges are already significant enough for the special education teachers, the situation became even worse due to the pandemic. According to the report of 11Alive News, "Governor Brian Kemp ordered all public schools, colleges and universities to close, starting March 18. Later, he would announce they would remain closed for the rest of the school year." The announcement made by the governor of Georgia led to a new academic setup and the respondents agreed that they had to make immediate adjustments to continue providing special services.

According to M-21-3, teaching during the pandemic was different. Instead of teaching virtually, the decision was to create *"little packets"* for the students to take home. They contain everything needed to get the work done. The students had to be followed up through constant phone calls or *"Facetime"*. It was challenging since not all the parents were responsive and supportive. The teachers were not fully aware about the students' progress. Involving the parents was also a struggle. M-21-3 also discussed how challenging it was to let the students finish the tasks since some parents did not care about their completion or did not know how to do it. A-21-4 even said that *"some parents were very concerned that they couldn't help their children."* These parents might know their children, but not everyone understood the special needs or how to provide special services. With the teachers being physically away from the students, it was a struggle for everyone. M-21-3 said that *"everything happened too quickly and they did not have enough time to prepare."* The teachers also made individual decisions to ensure that their students continued learning. The

teachers utilized printed worksheets, online exercises, Google Classroom, and video meetings.

Due to these adjustments, the students' academic performance suffered. S-23-1 said *"at home, they (the students) didn't have any help. They weren't able to do the tasks independently."* The sudden absence of a teacher to help the students keep up with the tasks had adverse effects. For instance, A-21-4 recalled the challenge some students had in using the Chromebook alone. *"For a child who wasn't used to that, it (Chromebook) was a struggle."* They eventually learned, but it took time.

The teachers still had to contact the parents at least once a month and ensure they were on the same page. Since the parents had to keep working, they were not always available for a conversation. Even with a successful contact, some parents struggled in implementing the plan. Most respondents also agreed that everyone did not have a clue about the next step, especially at first. They tried figuring things out as the classes went along. The teachers tried to make the most of the situation and changed based on the needs.

The return of the students to the classroom did not solve the challenges. A-21-4 recalled how frustrated some parents were since students were in and out of the class. The school policy requires not only students who tested positive to isolate, but everyone who got exposed. The inconsistent class attendance became a challenge for both the students and teachers. The attitude of the students also changed after months of studying from home. S-23-1 said *"...they did turn in work when they returned... They were kind of unmotivated to do anything. Lazy is a good word. Basically, they had done nothing or very little for several months."* The respondents said that returning to a regular classroom set up is like starting over again. They had to clarify the classroom policies and remind the students of the old routines. The

teachers also had to establish communication practices from the ground. The pandemic was an unforeseen phenomenon and there were no policies in place at that time for everyone to follow. The respondents believe they tried their best to communicate with the parents and students given the situation.

The issues raised by the respondents also stemmed from the fact that there are not enough special education teachers in the field. M-7-5 thinks that the system of identifying the students is not perfect. Some students might be “*gifted*” and they do not necessarily belong in either a self-contained or inclusive class. However, since there are not enough teachers in the system, these students might end up in a wrong class. Some gifted students are even grouped with students with behavioral issues and they cannot maximize their potentials. S-23-1 also believes that there are more cases of students diagnosed with special needs in the past few years, but the number of people taking up a degree in special education has not increased. Apart from the low wage, there is also a perception issue that led to the shortage. H-24-2 said “*I have kids ask me, so, when are you going to be a real teacher? I think there’s a perception or stigma. I think that makes it difficult to get people to come in.*” Not all students see special education teachers as “*real teachers*” and it discourages potential educators. Even before the pandemic, teacher shortage has already been an issue and it was only amplified by the health crisis. The Bureau of Labor Statistics “projected the need for 37,600 new special education teachers between 2020 and 2030 to keep up with demand. Right now, special education administrators are turning to long-term substitutes, some totally untrained to meet the needs of student with disabilities, and other short-term fixes to ensure a teacher in every classroom.” The pandemic only highlighted an issue that was already present in the system. Ultimately, the students suffer since their needs are not addressed due to the shortage of teachers who can

provide adequate social services. They also suffer when dealt with by someone who does not understand their communicative and academic needs.

“I think it was harder with special needs kids since not everyone has a device to do any work on Google Classroom. They eventually adjusted to the new study setup, but it took time.” [S-23-1]

“I think with Covid, it was just a different situation. Everything just got suspended. So, I don’t know. It was just weird... It was pretty difficult teaching then since we still have massive quarantines and constant changes and adjustments were necessary.” [H-24-2]

“At that time, I developed, not necessarily an online class with the students. I did call the parents to stay in touch with them. I created a little packet for my students to take home with them- everything they needed to do to finish their work. I had to make the most of the situation.” [M-21-3]

“That was a challenge. The students had their cellphones and that’s how I communicated with them. I would call them and text them too... They had computers, so I will message them the instructions through text or email. But, when a child wasn’t used to that, it was a struggle.” [A-21-4]

Table 5*Themes and Sub-themes on the Inside and Outside the Classroom Communication Challenges*

Sub-themes	Themes
Disabilities may hinder the understanding of concepts Students interpret instructions differently Lack of ability to comprehend tasks and activities Overwhelmed students refuse to accept information	Misunderstanding
Throwing tantrums due to overstimulation Inability to focus on, and finish the tasks Refusal to act appropriately despite explanation Triggers cause behavioral changes	Behavioral Issues
Failure to return calls and emails Socio-economic factors affect the ability to respond Insufficient investment in the students' education Rejects call due to busy schedule	Lack of Response
Unaware of the behavioral issues Insufficient knowledge of the medical condition Late diagnosis and IEP placement	Unclear Understanding of the Children's Special Needs
The need to change based on the situation Unfamiliarity with the new setup Lack of policies due to an unprecedented phenomenon Inconsistent communication Teacher shortage was exacerbated by the pandemic	Struggle to Adapt to the Changes

Recommendations and Solutions to Communication Challenges

Awareness and Sensitivity

After discussing the communication issues inside and outside the classroom, the respondents also provided recommendations and solutions. A common response is realizing that the students and parents are different. No two people are alike and teachers have to deal with them differently. M-21-3 recalled an incident about a student who threw a tantrum in the class. *“He doesn’t want you to touch him. He just wants you to let him work it out. He will go to the sensory area and he just has to work it out on his own.”* On the other hand, another student wanted to feel cared for and responded to. *“If he’s having tantrums, just hold him, and it might work for him.”* Special education teachers have to be aware of what works best for the student. M-7-5 shared a similar story where she used different tools to address behavioral challenges. *“Some people like the squishy objects (Fig. 8), but other people don’t like the way they feel. They like the way they squish, but they don’t like the texture.”* It is critical to know what works for the students to de-escalate the behavioral problems.

Figure 8

Squishy toys

Sales, R. (2022, December), *Students with anxiety may calm down with the aid of these toys* [Photography].

M-7-5 also said the same about what the administrators can do. The respondent recalled that during the Autism Awareness Month a few years ago, there was an event where general education students had the chance to ask students with autism about how it feels to have one. The special needs student gladly responded to the questions. After the event, the general education students became more sensitive in dealing with their peers. *“Once they walk in the room, everybody was loud, they will all of a sudden get quiet. They didn’t treat them like an outcast, like a SPED kid, like a “C” group kid.”* M-7-5 disclosed that it was her child with autism who was involved in the event and hoped that it can happen again to increase the sensitivity level among the students. When everyone understands what students with special needs go through, there will be more understanding. It includes not only the other students, but teachers and parents. Communication with the special needs students starts by knowing who they are and providing their needs. *“I have a magnifier for somebody who can’t see close up, and it’s just on paper. He can see the computer close up; he just can’t see on paper.”* M-7-5 also opened up to being a parent to a child with special needs and how it helped heightened her sensitivity to the students. Instead of getting frustrated that some students misbehave, she finds the root cause and deal with it.

S-23-1 shared a similar recommendation. *“We need some type of mentoring program or peer tutoring to help improve their relationship with each other.”* The respondent believes that communication challenges exist in the class because the general education students do not clearly understand why students with special needs act a certain way or responds to stimuli differently than they do.

M-7-5 said, *“I don’t think that there’s such a thing as bad kids. I only think there’s only bad choices and people not letting them taking responsibility for their actions.”* Understanding the students when they misbehave and providing appropriate

consequences can help. The teachers are only capable of doing it when they understand where the students are coming from. H-24-2 also shared a strategy she used to deal with communication challenges in the class. *“I have this wonderful little flip book (Fig. 9) on classroom management... I use tricks from that. In the classroom, I’ve tried to tailor everything to their individual personalities.”* A-21-4, on the other hand, use appropriate seating arrangements and other devices to help deal with these issues (Fig. 10). Again, it loops back to the idea that the students are different and the teachers have to be aware of what they need to deal with the challenges.

Figure 9

Classroom management flip book

Sales, R. (2022, December), H-2-4-2 discussed the use of this book to guide her in dealing with the students' behavioral issues [Photography].

Figure 10

A-21-4's classroom

Sales, R. (2022, December), *She utilizes unique seating arrangements to ensure class participation. She also uses the touchscreen device to play media files* [Photography].

In regards to the parents, the respondents also agreed about getting to know them better. It is easy to judge these parents if they failed to respond and conclude that they do not care enough about their children's education. However, the respondents saw the challenges faced by these parents and their deeper understanding of what they have gone through helped improve their relationship. H-24-2 said *"...with parents, I try to do email more. Let's say that made a big difference, so I am still trying it. I started sending notes home with the kids frequently. I have also sent a progress report every week, and that seems to help. That seems to improve the communication."* M-7-5 shares the same belief. *"You have to know your students and you have to know your parents. I call it handling parents with kid gloves. You don't know them. You only know them through the children, and the children's eyes."* She

provided an example of parental communication. When talking to parents from a more affluent family, the approach is different. Even the word choices are different. When the parents are from an impoverished family, her tone and approach differ. *“The point is to level it with the parents and communicate to them accordingly. But you can’t treat them like they’re incompetent.”* The parents have a crucial role in their children’s development. Hence, solving communication challenges is a must. The respondents agreed that when they can communicate their thoughts to the parents well, they become better partners in developing the students with special needs.

“You would not believe the unity after that. And, the sensitivity to whenever these kids would walk in there, they know they have sensitivity issues. They responded better after knowing the needs of the students with autism.” [M-7-5]

“I think the students, especially the high school, need to have a social skills class- how to understand and get along and with other kids. I think this should extend to general education students... So, there’s no way to teach the children the same way.” [S-23-1]

“I’ve tried to tailor everything to their individual personalities. I have to be aware about what is necessary to improve their behavior.” [H-24-2]

“You just have to try to tread lightly and put yourself in their shoes.” [A-21-4]

"It goes back to individual plan. Every student, every autistic child, there's no one that is alike." [M-21-3]

Prioritizing Students' Needs

The respondents also mentioned the instances when they thought about giving up. M-21-3 recalled that after years of teaching students with special needs in the elementary level, the offer to teach high school was a significant challenge. Instead of turning it down, it was taken as a motivation to be better. It was all about realizing that these students have no one to turn to, and their presence as special education teachers is necessary. *"I have a student now whom I have to help clean herself up because she isn't able to do that. That's not for everybody. It's not her fault. She can't help it. She didn't ask for it. If I can help her, I am going to."* M-21-3 sees the students' needs and respond based on what is in their best interest. After years of teaching, M-21-3 realized that the best way to communicate with the students is to know what they want to achieve (in the present or as a long-term goal) and be there to guide.

S-23-1 shared a communication challenge where some students were unable to express themselves. *"Some kids are coming to school with very little vocabulary. The parents aren't reading to them or talking to them."* Since S-23-1 saw how vocabulary is an issue for some students, it was given more emphasis. Addressing these communication challenges starts by knowing the root cause. Ultimately, when the students are capable of expressing themselves, they will feel satisfied. They can also function better in the class. S-23-1 also acknowledged that responding to the students' needs does not end by determining what they want at present. It also includes their plans after graduation. *"For high school, it includes a transition plan. We do a career interest inventory and interview them about their plans after high school."*

The approach in dealing with the students improve based on what they wish to achieve when special services are no longer available.

H-24-2 has a different perspective in solving communication challenges. *“I would like to see more co-planning between general education and special education teachers. I think it will improve the education among all the students and not just the special needs students.”* Since some students with special needs are in inclusive classes, the general education teachers also have to know them better. The lessons must be suitable not only to the needs of the general education students, but also the students with special needs. The learning process improves when the interest of everyone in the class is prioritized.

A-21-4 discussed a significant challenge on students who did not want to be treated differently. They hate the idea of being singled out for their disabilities. *“For instance, when they’re in a big class and I have to pull them on a small group for testing. They can’t stand that because they’re reminded, they’re special ed. So, that’s a big challenge. Sometimes, the child refuses to come with you.”* A-21-4 suggested that the best way to deal with this challenge is to explain to them that being in small testing groups is in their best interest. *“Look, I am not doing this to embarrass you. I don’t want to embarrass you. If you want to try something different, let’s talk about it. But this is helping you, and you know it.”* She also used an analogy regarding people wearing prescription glasses. She tried to explain to the students that some people need glasses to see better, but it does not make them less of a person or an embarrassment. When the students understand their accommodations and realize that these services are for their best interest, they become more responsive. They no longer throw tantrums or complain. A-21-4 does not only advocate for the students when they are around. She does the same during IEP meetings. *“I ask if there’s*

anything in particular, they want me to discuss on their behalf- if they're too shy to speak in front of everyone. I ask them questions and if they don't have any, I kind of prompt them what to say." A-21-4 believes that it is best when everyone involved in the IEP meetings see things from the perspective of the child in order to put their needs above everything else.

According to M-7-5, she sees things from a deeper perspective because she is also a mother to children with special needs. Therefore, as a parent and a teacher, she knows that communicative challenges can be solved by knowing what the students need. *"He's having a meltdown. Did something happen? I come in and say, the light right there is fixing to go out, and it's blinking. He's got a sensory overload today because he can see that and you can't."* Some students are unable to express their issues well and teachers have to be more sensitive in addressing their individual needs. It also takes time to get to know the students and it is critical to see things from their perspective. *"I'm going to look for stuff that we don't look for. Is somebody writing with a different lead pencil that will send off a sensory to their ears? Is there a substitute? Did they not get their breakfast the way they normally do that day? Anything that is off of their normal routine, I'm going to focus on that, and not because they're having a meltdown."* The idea is to know the reasons behind the behavioral challenges and solving them instead of dwelling on the fact that the students misbehaved again. For instance, instead of getting frustrated with students who get overstimulated with paper testing because of the black ink used, the focus is on the solution. In this instance, M-7-5 used colored binders (Fig. 11) to offer a pop of color on the paper and reduce anxiety. Coming to the class with an open mind also helps address the students' needs. According to M-7-5, it is easy to judge the students and treat them all the same. They might seem problematic, but they do not have the same

issues. Therefore, she starts by studying every student. *“I pull the folders and look at their history and see what I am going into. I don’t want somebody else’s feedback first. Let me go ahead and have an open mind in what is going on.”*

Figure 11

Colored binders

Sales, R. (2022, December), *As described by M-7-5, these things are useful to students who get overwhelmed by answering tests on papers* [Photography].

The discussion also geared towards the reasons behind why the respondents decided to become a special education teacher in the first place. A common theme in their response is that they are doing it *“for people who can’t help themselves.”* M-7-5 is a parent to children with special needs and understands how challenging it is for these children to not have someone who understands them. A-21-4 recalled her experience growing up with a cousin with special needs. When they became adults, it became clearer to her that they will never be on the same level of mental maturity. She also discussed about students coming back to her and thanking her for

encouraging them to succeed in life. S-23-1 recalled a similar experience and felt rewarded for it. M-21-3 highlighted the differences in the students' needs and how she felt blessed to be an instrument to address their issues. While the job can be challenging, it is ultimately a rewarding experience.

When asked about what they think can help encourage more people to pursue the same path that they did, the respondents were quite apprehensive. Some believe that the salary will always be an issue. However, they also acknowledge that more people need to understand what the job entails and how satisfying it can be. They claim that anyone who decides to be a special education teacher must see it as a "calling" and believe that it is where they need to be. They also have to stop being fearful about the idea of teaching students with different needs and see them as any other student.

"Always be mindful of the students when they come to school. It is always hard for them. I have a copy of the student's IEP, including the services, grades, behavioral plan, and transition plan to know what they need to achieve." [S-23-1]

"I think being a special education teacher means helping the children to realize the best part of themselves- to show them how to bring that out; helping them to become successful." [H-24-2]

"You have to figure out what the students need as a teacher, a special need teacher. It's not a black and white- here's how we're going to do it. It's a whole rainbow of mixed colors and emotions and strategies." [M-21-3]

“These kids need everything they can get to. They don’t need to fall through a crack. They need to be supported and encouraged and pushed and have expectations because they’re worthy too.” [A-21-4]

“I study the cases of every student and the parents. I need to go into it with an open mind and determine what is necessary to meet the needs of the students. [M-7-5]

Table 6

Themes and Sub-themes on the Recommendations and Solutions to Communication Challenges

Sub-themes	Theme
Understanding where they are coming from Communicate using approaches that consider individual differences Empathize with their needs before taking actions Utilize IEP to remember individual needs and goals Tread lightly and use kid gloves when necessary	Awareness and Sensitivity
Students have different needs and concerns that have to be addressed Be open-minded and never judge the students immediately Encourage the students to push harder because they are capable Know what can help the students feel satisfied and successful	Prioritizing Students’ Needs

Synthesis of Themes and Sub-themes

No two communication experiences are the same when it comes to teaching students with special needs. The respondents made it clear that every student is unique, and so are the parents. Their lived experiences revealed that communication can only be successful when there is sufficient understanding given to the students with special needs. Since they are unable to communicate like regular students due to their mental, physical, or emotional issues, appropriate approaches are necessary.

The communication challenges centered around miscommunication and behavioral issues, which are interconnected. When the students are unable to communicate their thoughts and intentions, they misbehave. With the right communication tools and strategies, the students start to act appropriately and pursue their interests. The people around them also have to be aware of their unique needs and strive to understand them instead of placing immediate judgments. The communicative process must also focus on the students' interests and laying out a path to help them reach their individual goals. Given the themes that emerged from the responses, I theorize "*cognizant-sensitive communication*" as the process where the messenger delves deeper into the abilities, thoughts, interests, and even limitations of the receiver to formulate, select, structure, and relay the message.

Cognizant-sensitive communication applies to the students with special needs since they have communicative limitations. These students are also unable to process visual cues, spoken and written information, in the same manner as the students without special needs. They may be more sensitive to things that people without disabilities may ignore, including lights, sounds, and gestures.

This theory conforms with the contact theory. Allport's (1954) contact theory as cited by McKay (2018) states that our stereotypical associations and biases will

decrease as we get to know and understand the experiences of others through meaningful, equal status, and collaborative contact. Allport (1954) first proposed the theory that social contact will improve relationships between members of majority and minority groups. This theory has been used to explain a great deal about human relations, particularly in terms of prejudice and difference. Once we eliminate such biases, it is easier to communicate with these students and see them as equal. Despite their communicative limitations and barriers, students with special needs are still capable of expressing themselves. The idea of cognizant-sensitive communication takes it a step further. Upon establishing contact and relationship, the messenger must consciously use the obtained information to hold a conversation. As the relationship deepens, the nature of communication also improves along with the efficiency in delivering the message.

This research was also grounded on the interpretative and interaction theories of communication. It suggests that all forms of communication are grounded on meaning and interaction. The results of this study also conform with this theory. The communicative process will only be successful once both individuals involved see the meaning in what they do. Furthermore, this theory acknowledges that people are always communicating, be it through words, gestures, or facial expressions. Cognizant-sensitive communication applies the elements of this theory and suggests that the messenger always has to be aware of the receiver's needs before saying a word or making gestures. It acknowledges the importance of meaning in communication, but it is possible that the people involved in the process might have different interpretations or understanding of the meaning. Therefore, the messenger needs to see things from the perspective of the receiver to successfully communicate thoughts and elicit appropriate responses.

Miller County Schools offer both self-contained classes and inclusive classes. The placement of the students depends on their mental and physical capacity, and social skills. Parental consent is also necessary in determining where the students were placed. For full disclosure, I am a general education teacher in some inclusive classes. A few students with IEP are in my classes, and as prescribed by law, a certified special education teacher must be with these students when placed in a regular classroom setting. Hence, I added my perspective into this synthesis of response, but were qualified under my capacity as a general education teacher.

When discussing the lived communication experiences of the special education teachers with the students, two themes emerged; appropriate approaches and equality. Their responses revealed that while these students may be different in many ways, they have to be treated equally. They deserve to feel like they do not have special needs and are just as capable as the students without disabilities. However, the respondents also recognized that communication will only be successful when they use appropriate approaches. These responses are aligned with the best strategies for handling discipline issues as suggested by the National Association of Schools Psychologists (2002), "When students are given an appropriate education in a conducive environment, they improve behavior and performance. Appropriately implemented, proactive behavior support systems can lead to dramatic improvements that have long-term effects on the lifestyle, functional communication skills and problem behavior in individuals with disabilities or at risk for negative adult outcomes." Inappropriate communication practices could lead to frustration and will only exacerbate the problem.

While these themes were appropriate, their application in the classroom setting can be challenging. For instance, I have observed a significant challenge that the

respondents faced, especially during testing. They were torn between forcing the students to be in small groups or allowing them to stay with the rest of the class. When they decide to keep them with the rest of the students, they may do poorly in the test. When they decide to forcibly remove them from the class, it can be a humiliating experience for the students. The communicative processes involved in this instance can be extensive and exhausting. It could have already been a routine at some point, but it does not appear to be that way. Every time the students are asked to be in separate groups, it can be challenging. As a caveat, this issue does not apply to all the students.

The idea of equality can therefore be a challenge since students with special needs require different approaches. Sometimes, the approaches that the respondents deem appropriate can make the special needs students inferior. Conversely, the effort to make them feel equal might result to the inability to reach academic goals. However, the respondents have made it clear that equality is a principle they bear in mind each time they communicate with the students. While they have made adjustments based on the students' needs, they do not want them to feel different. Even when they decide to pull them out of the classes, they have to remind the students that the goal is to help them reach the same academic goals as the rest of the class. It is not meant to make them feel like they terrible in any way.

Communicating to students with special needs can be a dynamic process. There are days when these students would love to constantly conversate, but there are also some days when they do not want to have a conversation at all. Some students may have limited vocabulary, and others have speech impediments. As a general education teacher, I have seen the communicative processes taking place between the special needs teachers and the students. It usually happens when there

are individual tasks, including tests, and these students require accommodations. It may also happen when the students have questions that could not be addressed in a general setting, or they are hesitant to raise their hands and ask. While I may step in to help, the responsibility falls mainly into the hands of the special needs teacher.

Also, based on my observations, special needs teachers use multiple strategies to aid in the communicative process. Some students can be unruly when frustrated about what is going on inside the class. When they do not understand the lessons or they feel like they are behind everyone else, they may act out. Others may also choose to “shut down” and decide not to pay attention at all. Some students even have a very limited attention span, especially students diagnosed with ADHD and autism. Therefore, using appropriate approaches is necessary. It was a good thing that this theme came out of the responses since the concept was mentioned multiple times. It reveals that the teachers need aid to improve communication and it is not enough that they rely only on words and gestures. The use of technology is also an asset. Perhaps, better technology will be available in the future, and could reach rural schools in the United States, since they aid in the communicative processes.

The lived communication experiences of the respondents with the parents revealed three themes; understanding, building relationships, and truthful feedback. The role of communication is to ensure that everyone is on the same page. Both the teachers and parents take an active role in the students’ educational growth. The respondents revealed that parents have different qualities just like the students. Hence, they utilize the right approach to convey the message. Building a relationship with the parents takes time and it requires constant communication. Establishing a relationship is key in the communication process. The teachers feel more comfortable in expressing the truth about the students’ academic and behavioral performance

when the parties involved have maintained a good relationship. This idea conforms with other researches involving teacher-parent relationships. Welch & Sheridan (1995) said that parents and teachers in collaborative relationships depend on one another equally and reciprocally. The process of “coming together” in education requires a re-evaluation and recreation of roles, responsibilities, and relationships. Teachers and parents need to recognize their shared interests and responsibilities for the student, and work collaboratively to create better opportunities for the student (Epstein, 1995). Building a relationship with parents and working as partners will help ensure students success (Park, 2008; Prin & Tolso, 2008).

Communicating with parents also requires honesty. The respondents believe that the parents deserve to know the truth about their children. However, they also understand that these parents hear negativity all the time. In the past, they have mostly received information regarding developmental delays or behavioral challenges. They also worry about how their children socialize at school. Parents of students with disabilities may have concerns about the attitudes and acceptance of other, nondisabled students and those students' parents (Heward, 2003). In fact, parents of a young child with developmental delays had poorer self-rated general health than parents of comparably aged typically developing children (Eisenhower, Baker, & Blacher, 2008). For these reasons, special education teachers believe in the idea of treading lightly when talking to parents. There were discussions on the use of strategies to allow the discussion of the truth without adding more burden to the parents. Pairing positive and negative feedback help relieve the parents of their fear and anxiety.

Another strategy is to use appropriate words, tone, and structure, depending on the parents' socio-demographic profiles. Some parents are capable of

understanding medical and academic terms, while others are not. Some parents might also come from affluent families with high educational achievement. The respondents believe that the approach differs based on the parents' background. These results strengthen the idea of communication. It is the belief that the message can only be successfully relayed when the messenger takes the extra steps to identify the background of the receiver. For instance, the use of difficult words to a parent with limited vocabulary will only cause confusion. When parents are used to communicating using "slangs" or "vernaculars," they might not understand the message containing highly academic terms. The special education teachers have to be conscious about their word choices to facilitate a good conversation. It also boosts partnerships and ultimately benefit the child.

Based on my conversations with the school administrators and special needs teachers, a meeting with the IEP team is necessary in placing the student who may potentially have special needs. The succeeding meetings will only take place upon the request of the parent, teacher, or any other relevant member of the IEP team. The goal may include IEP modification or re-evaluation based on the current performance of the student. A parent conference may also be called to follow up on academic performance or behavioral issues in class. The conference will not necessarily modify the IEP, but will only include discussions on student performance or if there are issues that require immediate actions.

The nature of the conferences depends on the agenda, level of parental support, and student performance. Based on my observations, some meetings can be calm and straightforward. Everyone is on the same page and there were no disagreements on how to move forward. Other meetings can be tension-filled. It is more common when student behavior needs to be addressed and the parents tend to

be defensive. However, conferences are usually canceled due to scheduling conflicts and last-minute changes. Conferences may also take place via phone calls if the parents are unable to come to the school.

Understanding where the parents are coming from and why they have different levels of involvement require an open mind. The respondents highlighted the need to suspend judgment and get to know the parents first. During my observations, the teachers were mostly the listeners. They would rather understand the perspectives of the parents first before crafting the responses. Sometimes, these parents do not know where to begin, and the teachers prompted the conversation towards the set goal. I have also noticed that the concept of understanding as revealed in the research does not only apply during the conference. Some parents might seem eager to discuss issues during the meeting, but decide not to follow up once it is over. It also takes time before they communicate with the teachers again.

Based on my capacity as a general education teacher, being understanding can be challenging. Some parents will not return calls and emails despite constant reminders. It applies not only to the parents of students with special needs, but to other parents too. I have also observed that some parents stop communicating once the meeting is over and will not necessarily care if the issues were addressed after the conversation. Again, just like the theme that emerged in the responses, understanding is necessary. It might be easy to judge why these parents act a certain way, but there could be deeper reasons the teachers are unaware of. Suspending judgments can lead to a more honest and objective conversation. Tensions usually arise when the teacher decides to just be as defensive as the parent and offer responses without thinking about the right words to say. Understanding entails not only the ability to remain patient during the meeting, but in every step of the way. Without understanding,

the people involved in the conversation can easily lose sight of the goal of helping the students with special needs. Once both parties established a sense of understanding, building relationships may follow. It removes the barriers between the parents and teachers. However, building a relationship also poses a unique set of challenges. For instance, it will only happen under the assumption that the parents are willing to build such a relationship or constant communication takes places. While the administrators constantly remind the teachers to build a relationship with the parents, it remains challenging. The good thing, though, is that considering the size of the school and the number of students, it is easier to reach out to all the parents. It can be somewhat different in bigger schools where teachers have to deal with hundreds of students at a given school year.

The emerging theme on truthful feedback is probably among the hardest to do since it requires a careful selection of words. Sometimes, even with deep considerations, mistakes can still happen. Again, parents tend to be defensive when informed about their children's poor performance or behavior. As the respondents have mentioned, it is critical to choose the right words without hiding the truth from the parents. This strategy also improves over time as the communication between both parties continues. In my personal capacity as a general education teacher, truthful feedback can be challenging when the students present something else to their parents. The "truth" that the parents received from the teachers might be questioned since the students assured their parents about their good academic performance. Hence, it is also critical to include evidence, such as test results, when providing feedback to the parents. They will realize that the information received did not come out of thin air. Ultimately, the teacher-parent communication can take tons of setbacks, but keeping an open mind can be helpful. When everyone involved sees the purpose

of the communicative process as an avenue to help the students improve, it becomes more productive.

The respondents also raised the communication challenges experienced inside and outside the classroom. Misunderstanding and behavioral issues were the emerging themes for classroom challenges, while the lack of response and unclear understanding of the children's special needs were the themes emerging from communication outside the classroom. During the pandemic, the theme of the challenge experienced is struggle to adapt to the changes.

Since the students with special needs are incapable of communicating similar to the students without disabilities, misunderstanding became a prevailing challenge. The students interpret words and actions differently or are more sensitive to a stimulus. Failing to send the correct message may also lead to behavioral challenges. The student with a reading disability may lash out in anger due to his mounting frustration with his inability to decode words (Shore, 2013). The same is true when the special needs students interact with their peers without disabilities. The severe social skill impairments that students with emotional and behavioral problems often have could impede positive peer interactions and lead to rejection (Bradley et al., 2008). With an incorrect or inappropriate response from anyone in the academic environment, the behavior might worsen. Again, the concept of cognizant-sensitive communication apply when these challenges arise. When the teachers and peers do not understand what the students with special needs go through, they might not be aware of how they respond. The immediate reaction is to get angry or punish the students. However, according to Eckerd, M. (2011), "... children should not be punished for having a disability. None of us want children to be explosive, rude, and misinterpret the behavior of others. Yet, we have the right to demand that the school has sufficient

understanding to reduce the triggers for misbehavior and to teach the student how to adapt.”

As previously mentioned, some students with special needs can express frustration and decide not to complete their work. They may also act out because of how they feel at the moment. Misbehavior is common in both self-contained and inclusive classes. However, it is also crucial to note that it can happen to any student, and not only to students with special needs. The only difference are the factors that may affect how students with special needs react. They are more sensitive to things that students without special needs may ignore. The conversation with the respondents also revealed the challenges that come with the disciplinary actions resulting from the misbehavior. There are special rules that apply to these students, but they are not exempt from the consequences of their actions. There is always careful determination done by the teachers and school administrators in regards to appropriate consequences. Explaining them to the parents is another issue since they might question the severity of the punishment. Hence, the previous theme on understanding also applies in this regard. Students have the need to be understood when they misbehave to help them get through what they currently face. The respondents agreed that severe punishments usually do not work and may only exacerbate the problem.

When dealing with the parents, it was revealed that the lack of understanding of the children with special needs may also happen outside the school environment. At home, these children might feel misunderstood. While parents know more about their children’s needs, it does not necessarily apply to everyone. Not all parents have a clear grasp of their children’s medical and special needs. The respondents discussed the parents’ lack of knowledge on certain medical information. Hence, they

are unable to discuss pressing issues relevant to their children's behavior at school. The volume of information they receive, and the legal and technical terminology, many parents of students with disabilities find understanding special education materials and regulations daunting (Burke, 2013). Despite that, they are still eager to know and work with the teachers to help their children. The parents of preschool age children recently diagnosed with autism overwhelmingly reported wanting as much information about autism up front even when they recognized it might be overwhelming or difficult to absorb (Osborne & Reed, 2008). As such, cognizant-sensitive communication also applies to parents since the teachers have to be aware of the parents' needs and concerns when communicating with them. Understanding where they are in terms of caring for their children allows the teachers to carefully craft the message. In the process, it empowers the parents and makes them feel more involved. Empowerment is explained as the result of helping families to gain control over the events in their lives, and imparting abilities to aid them in getting what they want and need to raise a special needs child (Van Haren & Fiedler, 2008). Cognizant-sensitive communication becomes a tool for empowerment among parents of children with special needs.

Lack of response is another theme emerging out of the challenges experienced in dealing with the parents of students with special needs. While some parents are accessible, it is not always the case. The respondents discussed the challenge in reaching out to some. Despite that, they still tried various means to communicate. According to Buchori (2006), education shall fail without parents' participation. Clough & Nutbrown (2004) believe that the parents should be included in the school because information about processes, system and intervention in the school are needed by parents. While it can be frustrating to see the lack of response, teachers should focus on finding ways to connect with the parents. There could be various reasons behind

the lack of response. For instance, some parents are unable to accept their children's disabilities and decide not to get involved. Wiener (2003) suggests that some parents may place such value on achievement that they are unable to accept the existence, extent of, or implications of their children's learning disabilities. Another reason is the misaligned expectations. The parents and teachers are not on the same page regarding the students' education. The school thinks that the parents are expecting too much, given their child's abilities, while the parents accuse the school of focusing on their child's limitations (Russell, 2003).

Perhaps, the biggest factor affecting parental involvement is the economic background of the parents. The respondents revealed that some parents are unable to keep in touch since they have to work hard or were dealing with other issues at home. This is confirmed by the research conducted by Mandic, et al., (2012) showing that parental involvement indicates that a considerable number of low income, nonwhite parents of children with disabilities report a discrepancy between their actual and desired levels of parental involvement in the IEP process.

In regards to these challenges, the respondents expressed their concern with some parents who do not necessarily show that they care. Reaching out to them can be challenging due to various reasons, including the socio-demographic profile of the parents. In my personal experience as a general education teacher, scheduling an IEP meeting (through the special needs teacher) or parent conference takes time. Scheduling conflicts are always an issue. Despite emails and phone calls for follow-ups, some parents are still hard to reach. Hence, it is understandable that the respondents consider the lack of parental response as a significant challenge.

The emerging theme on the lack of understanding of the students' special needs came as a surprise. The respondents are middle and high school teachers. At

this age, one can expect that the parents have been involved in their children's development since the initial diagnosis. In most instances, parents understand their children better than anyone else. They are also the first ones to resolve situations involving misbehavior. Therefore, seeing this emerging theme is unexpected, but completely understandable. Not all parents are highly educated and their knowledge on their children's medical conditions might be limited. Their limited involvement could also be another reason for their lack of understanding. The teachers might also not know everything, but it is critical that they help the parents understand their children's conditions and limitations. It also results to a more consistent approach at home, and eventually produce the desired behavior. Ultimately, this challenge revealed the importance of having a strong partnership between the parents and teachers to guide the students with special needs in achieving their goals.

These communication challenges were heightened during the pandemic. The emerging theme from the discussion is the struggle to adapt to changes. Since the setup was something new for everyone, adjustment was difficult. Communication with both the parents and students became even more challenging. Some students were too dependent and unable to do the required tasks without teacher supervision. Parents also had to continue working and were not present to guide their children. Families with fewer financial resources may be especially vulnerable to COVID-19 impacts as a result of unstable, unsafe, or strained housing situations (Rogers & Power, 2020). It was a stressful situation for everyone involved, especially the students with special needs. Children's stress often manifests through changes in behaviors likely perceived to be challenging by parents (e.g., whining, hitting, sleep difficulties), contributing to parents' stress and parenting behaviors (Neece et al., 2012). The cognizant-sensitive communication theory applies regardless of the

communication obstacles encountered. Again, teachers are messengers and have to be more aware of what the parents and students are going through before or while communicating with them.

While I was not yet a part of the school system when the school closure due to the pandemic happened, I had similar experiences in a different school. I concur with the experiences of the teachers and how challenging it was to not have a blueprint given the circumstances. It was not easy balancing the completion of academic work and ensuring that everyone stays healthy. Dealing with the students in a classroom environment already poses tons of challenges. Having a completely different and new setup made the communicative process even worse. From the students' ability to comprehend instructions to the lack of technology to communicate, teachers had to deal with multiple obstacles. The uncertainty of the future, including the time it might take for the setup to persist also became a factor. It prevented the teachers from creating long-term plans since there might be immediate changes within a few days. Everyone has to take the challenges as they come and solve individual issues once they arise, instead of taking a more proactive approach. Ultimately, this unfortunate situation forced everyone to make the most of what is available and somehow continue the academic and communicative processes.

The discussion on the recommendations and solutions to the communication challenges faced revealed two emerging themes; awareness and sensitivity, and prioritizing students' interests. These themes helped solidify my concept of cognizant-sensitive communication. This concept begins with awareness. According to Gutwin et al. (1996) as cited by Röcker (2011), awareness can be seen both as a product and a process. The product is the state of understanding processes and actions in the real world, that enables people to interpret events, anticipate needs, and act appropriately.

The process is the continuous cycle of extracting information from the environment, integrating this information with existing knowledge, and using that knowledge to direct further perception. Hence, awareness in communication is a continuous process. It does not end when the message has been received. There must be a conscious effort to understand the recipient in delivering the message, and act appropriately based on the obtained information. Students with special needs and their parents can benefit when the concept of cognizant-sensitive communication is applied to the conversation. Remaining mentally aware of thoughts and behaviors, as well as of the background and progression of a conversation, can help a speaker communicate more effectively and appropriately across all channels (Hendrix & Morrison, 2020).

This benefit of awareness in communication does not only apply in special education. In a study conducted by Kaihlanen, et al. (2019) in the field of healthcare, it was revealed that increased awareness might facilitate the communication between healthcare professionals and patients, which is a crucial component of quality healthcare. Awareness also plays a key role in keeping work groups motivated (Walendowski & Ranganthan, 2002) and helps to establish a sense of community (Whittaker & Bradner, 2000). The same holds true with sensitivity in communication. Akgün (2010) emphasized the necessity of implementing a program that enables more sensitive communication and interaction with pupils with intellectual disabilities. In healthcare, outcomes associated with the use of culturally sensitive communication include increased patient and family satisfaction, improved adherence to treatment regimens, better engagement in patient and family centered care and improved health outcomes (Betancourt et al., 2014).

Prioritizing students' interests is another theme emerging from the recommendations to solve the challenges in special education. Identifying the

students' current needs and determining potential transition plans can help them achieve their goals. Therefore, it is crucial to communicate based on their interests. It helps to allow the students to share their views and perceptions instead of forcing them into a path that does not appeal to them. This conforms with the idea of self-directed learning. The teachers serve as a bridge to allow the students to get to the finish line, but they have to take the lead. Self-directed learning is a process where individuals take primary charge of planning, continuing and evaluating their learning experiences (Merriam et al., 2007). According to Candy (1990), self-directed learning is a way of turning individuals into lifelong learners. This also aligns with Bandura' self-efficacy theory. Self-efficacy expectations refer to a person's beliefs concerning his or her ability to successfully perform a given task or behavior and were perceived to be major mediators of behavior and behavior change (Bandura, 1977). Cognizant-sensitive communication pushes for self-efficacy. Teachers have to be mindful of what their students want to happen and help them become more independent. The communicative process is necessary in identifying what the needs are, and in creating a path to address them. In the day-to-day interactions between the teachers and students with special needs, being conscious helps the teachers determine what to say and eliminate unnecessary discussions.

The themes emerging from the recommendations played a critical role in the formation of the theory in this study. It revealed that it does not matter what the communicative challenges are. The special needs teachers should always return to their students' goals and keep them in mind in making decisions and planning the course of actions. Sometimes, it is easy to get overwhelmed when various challenges are on the plate at once. These recommendations show that with awareness and sensitivity, achieving the goals is possible. For instance, during a tense parent

conference, the people involved disagreed on several matters. From the cause of the student's misbehavior to the potential solutions, the parents, teachers, and administrators failed to come to an immediate agreement. However, when the tension started to subside, the conversation began to smoothen. The parties involved came up with a compromise. Even the tone of the conversation began to change and the choices of words also softened. Perhaps, the realization that everyone is on the same page in helping the student, allowed the communicative process to succeed.

There is no doubt that the lived communication experiences of special education teachers are challenging. Regardless of the challenges, these teachers are aware that their priority is to provide services to their students. They are only after their best interest. Students with special needs are in a spectrum. No two students are deemed alike and their needs also vary. The communicative strategies that apply to one may not be applicable to another. This holds true with their parents as well. This research theorizes "cognizant-sensitive communication" as it addresses the individuality of the people involved in communication. It goes beyond simply relaying the message, but understanding the best way to deliver it. The needs and characteristics of the students will evolve over time, and applying the concept of cognizant-sensitive communication will help build understanding.

Theorizing the concepts required multiple readings of the responses and a deeper analysis of the emerging themes. Everything boiled down to the type of communication that the special needs teachers go through on a daily basis due to the nature of their profession. Cognizant-sensitive communication is the best way to describe their lived communication experiences since they have to practice it at all times. There are also potential repercussions for not doing so. These teachers cannot jeopardize their relationship with the students when they say the wrong words. It may

also lead to a worsened behavior and a regression of the positive changes observed over the years. It could take years for progress to happen, but only seconds to change everything. For instance, students with severe anxiety and depression take a long time to feel confident of themselves and trust the people around them. Talking to them using inappropriate words or tone could fully erode their trust. The same thing applies to parents. Relationship building does not happen overnight. Even constant conversations are still insufficient earning their trust. As expressed by the respondents, they have to adjust their manner of expressing themselves depending on who they are talking to. They always have to be conscious when they communicate to clearly send the message across and achieve the goal. Hence, the need to be cognizant and sensitive is the essence of the lived communication experiences of the special needs teachers.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents a summary of the findings revealed in this phenomenological research. It also includes the conclusions formed after analyzing the results and recommendations for future researchers.

SUMMARY

This research was conducted to give special education teachers a voice by sharing their lived communication experiences. It aimed to answer the research question, “*What are the lived communication experiences of the special education teachers at Miller County Schools?*” While previous researches shed light on the perceptions of special education teachers through quantitative methods, this study focused on the communication aspect of the job using a phenomenological research approach. It delved deeper into the views of the teachers on the different facets of the job. It was crucial to use this approach since according to Boss, et al., 1996, an accurate presentation of the experience under study is more important in this approach than the ability to claim that the findings apply to across situations or people. The communication experiences of the respondents were analyzed using the techniques in a phenomenological study.

Five respondents were interviewed for this research. They were certified special education teachers at Miller County Schools. There were also observations made on their classes, IEP meetings, and parent conferences. The researcher used the

unstructured interview approach and only provided prompts to ensure a natural flow in the conversation.

The interviews were recorded and transcribed. The respondents were given a copy of the transcriptions to validate their statements. The researcher used the analysis procedure adopted from Giorgi, 1985; 1997; 2003 to interpret the responses. After reading the transcriptions, bracketing the statements, discriminating of meaning units, and reflecting on their meanings, essential themes emerged from the study.

In regards to the lived communication experiences with the students, the emerging themes were appropriate approaches and equality. These themes suggest that while the students might be different in terms of their attributes and needs, they deserve equal treatment. Appropriate approaches are necessary to cater to their needs.

The lived communication experiences with the parents revealed three essential themes; understanding, building relationships, and truthful feedback. Just like the students, the parents are also different and approaching them also requires an understanding of their background. It also pays to build relationships with them to convey the message regarding their children's needs properly. This message must be truthful since it is the only way to carve a path forward. Hiding the reality from the parents will only worsen the situation.

The challenges inside and outside the classroom revealed five essential themes; misunderstanding, behavioral issues, lack of response, lack of understanding of the children's special needs, and struggle to adapt to changes. Like any other communicative experience, dealing with special needs students and their parents can be challenging. In class, misunderstanding is possible since the students are not equipped with the same mental and physical attributes that regular students may have.

Their disabilities might lead to misunderstanding. When they are unable to express themselves, it leads to frustration. Hence, behavioral issues are possible. Students act out when they do not feel understood and their needs met. The challenges outside the classroom are related to the conversation with the parents. Communicating with them can be challenging due to their lack of response. Even when they respond, they might not fully understand their children's needs. Ensuring that they stay on the same page can be challenging. These issues were exacerbated during the pandemic when adjustments were necessary. There were struggles with all parties involved in the educational process due to the immediate changes. The new setup was not easy for the students and not all the parents can look after them. The teachers were also physically away from the students and it affected their ability to communicate properly.

These challenges yielded recommendations and solutions. The two essential themes emerging from this discussion are awareness and sensitivity and prioritizing the students' needs. Addressing the communication issues is possible when the teachers go beyond what they see and try to understand the students and their parents for behaving a certain way. It also includes the other members of the academic community. With a deeper understanding of the students, communicating with them becomes easier. Ultimately, the teachers have to consider what is in the best interest of the students when communicating with them.

These themes and sub-themes led to the conceptualization of "*cognizant-sensitive communication*." This research theorizes this concept after analyzing the lived communication experiences of the respondents. Cognizant-sensitive communication refers to the process where the messenger delves deeper into the abilities, thoughts, interests, and even limitations of the receiver to formulate, select, structure, and relay the message. This theory applies to the students with special

needs as they may have communicative limitations. Awareness is where understanding begins. It includes their physical and mental needs, challenges in the classroom, and other areas of sensitivity. This concept also applies to the parents. As identified in the research, the parents may differ because of their socio-economic background. Cognizant-sensitive communication allows for a more organized conversation which leads to the proper delivery of the message.

The results of the study were validated through member checking. The respondents were given the detailed analysis of the results and confirmed the accuracy. The findings of this research cannot be generalized to all the special education teachers and it was not the goal in the first place. However, it allowed a deeper view into the lived experiences of the respondents. The use of the phenomenological research approach is about the meaning of the human experience and the world. The aims of phenomenological research are to reach the essence of the individuals' lived experience of the phenomenon while ascertaining and defining the phenomenon (Cilesiz, 2010). Lourer (1967) implied that the unique source of absolute existence is based on what the person thinks, feels, and perceives.

CONCLUSIONS

“Cognizant-sensitive communication” is the best way to describe the lived experience of the special education teachers. It is the ability to be discerning when communicating to the students with special needs, including their parents. The communicative process is unique since these students have varied needs due to their physical and/or mental limitations. Cognizant-sensitive communication is the concept of going beyond the surface to understand the recipient of the message so they may fully grasp it. It can be theorized that the special education teachers are not only

speaking out their minds when dealing with the students, but they filter the information based on what they believe is appropriate for the interaction.

Based on the themes emerging from this study, it can also be concluded that no two students with special needs are alike. They differ in many ways, including the special services necessary to address their needs. Treating them equally is essential to avoid making them feel different and inferior. However, the right approach will ensure the delivery of special services.

The study also revealed that the parents are just like the students and their socio-demographic background affects their involvement in their children's education. It takes a while to establish a relationship with them, and it is necessary to start with a sense of understanding. Over time, truthful feedback is possible since they no longer feel bad about receiving bad news regarding their children's performance. Instead, they become more supportive. They also have a better understanding of the special services.

The lived communication experiences also provided a deeper insight into the primary role of the teacher- finding a way to prioritize students' interests. Regardless of the teaching or communication strategy used in the class, everything must gear towards the students' needs. The goal is to respond to the current needs and understand where the students might be heading to create an appropriate transition plan. While the special needs services might no longer come from the teachers after finishing high school, the established transition plan will serve as the framework for the path ahead.

Communicative challenges are always a part of the special education teachers' lives. There are struggles both inside and outside the classroom. Students who are unable to express themselves might end up misbehaving. The lack of responses from

the parents when reached out to regarding their children's education is also another challenge. At the height of the pandemic, the sudden adjustment to the new reality highlighted the bigger challenges faced by the special education teachers. To a certain extent, these challenges were among the reasons why hiring more teachers became even more difficult. The success of the communicative processes depends on the ability to adjust to these challenges. The actual responses might be different from expected responses, but it is not the end of the road. Teachers still have to adjust until the issues are addressed.

While the lived experiences of the teachers can be challenging, they still agree that being in this field can be rewarding. The success of their students is also their success. Seeing them transition from needing special services to full independence year down the road makes these respondents decide to remain in their profession.

RECOMMENDATIONS Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are advanced:

1. The special education teachers in inclusive classes with a general education teacher must be given more opportunity to discuss what is best for the students with special needs present in the class. Awareness on the appropriate pedagogical and communicative approaches must extend to the general education teacher.
2. There should be an opportunity for general education students to understand the challenges faced by the students with special needs through a dialogue, mentoring program, or peer tutorial activities. The administrators have to initiate these activities for the benefit of the entire student body. As awareness is deemed the beginning of successful communication, it helps

students with special needs to receive the chance to be understood by their peers.

3. Communication tools and assistive technology are essential in improving communication in the class, and are among the appropriate approaches that teachers can utilize. The use of sensory room even for inclusive classes can help the teachers in dealing with the challenges, in communication or otherwise.
4. For future researchers, the lived communication experiences of special education teachers in bigger public-school systems in the US are worth exploring. Their views might be different due to the disproportionate number of students requiring special services.
5. Future researchers should look into the lived communication experiences of the students with special needs, and distinguish their experiences in self-contained and inclusive classes.
6. Future researchers may look into the interactions in a special education class using an ethnomethodological qualitative research approach. It aims to see how the individuals involved in the process make sense of everyday interactions.
7. The reasons behind the lack of special education teachers can be further looked into by future researchers. It may include ways to solve this problem from the perspective of the administrators.
8. There are specific communicative challenges during the IEP meeting that are worth studying. The dynamics of the IEP team members' interaction and how it impacts student growth can be studied using a quantitative approach.

9. The lived experiences of the parents of children with special needs have been studied, but researchers can focus on the communicative aspect, both at home and in other settings.

10. The concept of cognizant-sensitive communication is theorized based on the responses of the special education teachers being the messenger in the communicative process. Future researchers can look into the validity of this concept in other areas.

Limiting biases. The study has given me a different perspective about teaching and communicating to students with special needs. I am also a general education teacher and has taught inclusive classes in the last six years. However, I am yet to teach self-contained classes or be a special education teacher following students with special needs in inclusive class environments. The lived communication experiences of the teachers on the ground are insightful. They have a perspective that is different from general education teachers, parents, and administrators. Some respondents discussed the potential tension between the general education teachers and special education teachers since they are coming from different perspectives. They also mentioned that the goals of the general education teachers might gear towards the class as a whole, while special education teachers have to pay attention to accommodations and the impact of the interactions to students with special needs. Hence, I made sure that this bias did not impact my analysis of the findings. I allowed the respondents' points of view to emerge and bracketed my views, as they are irrelevant to the conversation. My personal views and observations in the presentation of the results were qualified based on my role in the classroom.

Observing classes, IEP meetings, and parent conferences are also a part of the procedures in conducting this research. Since Miller County Schools is a small school system, some students in the classes and conferences that I have observed were also my students. I have personal knowledge about their academic performance and behavior in my class. However, this research is not about my communication and interaction with the students or the strategies I have used in the past. It is centered around the lived experiences of the special education teachers. Hence, it did not matter whether or not I agree with their statements. The unstructured interview allowed me to provide prompts to further clarify issues without distorting the respondents' narratives. Issues relevant to my role as a general education teacher were discussed in separate occasions and were off the record. Again, my observations were qualified in presenting the analysis of the results.

I have a Doctorate in Special Education and the concepts mentioned by the respondents were familiar to me. I also have experiences in handling students with special needs and their parents, both in Thailand and in the United States. My lived experiences may or may be similar with the respondents, but it did not affect this study. The focus was only on allowing the respondents' narratives to flow and for the themes to emerge after the data analysis. I started this research with an open mind and maintained the same attitude until the end.

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LIST OF APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Letter to the Principal

December 8, 2022

Mr. Tommy Tabb
Principal

Dear Mr. Tabb,

Good day!

I would like to ask for your permission to conduct an interview and observe the classes of selected special education teachers at the school. It is in line with my current dissertation entitled, "The Lived Communication Experiences of the Special Education Teachers at Miller County Schools." The research aims to determine the essence of student and parental communication through the narratives of the special education teachers. The interview will last for an hour or more, depending on the nature and duration of the responses.

I will arrange the interview schedule with the selected teachers and request for their individual permission to be interviewed. I will also observe some classes and parent conferences. Strict confidentiality will be observed throughout the process. The names of the students who might be discussed during the interview or noted during the observation will not appear in the research publication. Once the research is over, I would be glad to share with you the results.

Rest assured, the research is aimed at helping improve special education in Miller County Schools and I will remain truthful to the findings based on the collected data.

Sincerely,

Rom Kenneth B. Sales, PhD, EdD
Doctor of Communication Student
University of the Philippines Open University

Approved: Tommy Tabb

APPENDIX B

Letter to the Respondents

December 8, 2022

Special Education Teacher
Miller County School

Dear _____,

Good day!

I would like to ask for your permission to be interviewed as a respondent for my research. I am currently working on a dissertation entitled, "The Lived Communication Experiences of the Special Education Teachers at Miller County Schools." The research aims to determine the essence of student and parental communication through the narratives of the special education teachers. The interview will last for an hour or more, depending on your response. I am also observing your classes and parental conferences (when possible).

I am hoping that we can have the interview on December 14-19, 2022 (whatever date suits you best). If you're unavailable or if there are other dates that you prefer, please let me know. I would be glad to reschedule the interview.

Rest assured, strict confidentiality will be observed throughout the process. The names of the students who might be discussed during the interview or noted during the observation will not appear in the research publication. Once the research is over, I will share with you the results.

Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Sincerely,

Rom Kenneth B. Sales, PhD, EdD
Doctor of Communication Student
University of the Philippines Open University

APPENDIX C

Sample Questions to the Respondents

1. What is it like to communicate with the special needs students?
2. What is in special education that made you decide to stay?
3. What is it like to communicate with the parents of special needs students?
4. Can you give examples of the challenges faced in your job as a special education teacher?
5. How do you deal with these challenges in class?
6. What was it like to communicate with the students at the height of the pandemic?
7. What do you use to help improve your communication with the students? How about the parents?
8. Have you received complaints or faced severe challenges in communicating with the parents?
9. What solutions can you suggest to prevent these challenges from getting worse?
10. Do you have any advice to future special educators?
11. What have you learned from your years of being a special needs teacher?

APPENDIX D

Audit Trail

Date	Activity	Notes
December 8, 2022	Sent a letter to the principal to seek permission to conduct the study	
December 9, 2022	Sent a letter to the respondents to be a part of the research	The conduct of the research is contingent upon the principal's approval
December 12, 2022	Principal signed the permission letter and approved the conduct of the study	The principal informed me to also notify the director of special education via phone call or text to keep her in the loop
December 13, 2022	Received approval responses from the identified respondents	The respondents informed me via phone call or came to my classroom to discuss their availability
December 14, 2022	Observed M-21-3's self-contained class Observed S-23-1's inclusive class	Took notes and photos during these meetings and observations without interfering with the discussions or getting involved in any way
December 15, 2022	Attended an IEP meeting with H-24-2 Attended a parent conference with S-23-1	Observed the interactions and communication flow
December 16, 2022	Observed H-24-2's self-contained class (study skills subject) Observed A-21-4's inclusive classes	
December 19, 2022	Interviewed S-23-1	It happened during the 7 th period since we share the same planning period (02.30-4.00pm)
December 20, 2022	Interviewed H-24-2 Interviewed M-21-3	The interview was scheduled in the morning since the bell schedule was different during this day due to testing (10.00-11.30am) The interview took place in her classroom. The students were dismissed

Date	Activity	Notes
		early after testing (02.00-3.30pm)
December 21, 2022	Interviewed A-21-4	The interview took place in her classroom during my planning period since we share the same planning period (02.30-4.00pm)
December 22, 2022	Interviewed M-7-5	This interview was rescheduled multiple times due to conflict. (11.00-12.30pm)
December 23-26, 2022	Transcription of all interviews	
December 27, 2022	All the respondents received a transcription of their interview for correction and/or clarification	Only S-23-1 and H-24-2 made corrections on their statements and these changes were immediately reflected on the transcript
December 28, 2022- January 5, 2023	Analysis of the collected data (bracketing, coding, writing initial results, etc.)	
January 9, 2023	Member-checking	Respondents were given the initial results and interpretation of their responses
January 11, 2023	Feedback from respondents	The feedback was taken into account and revisions were made from the original interpretation